

FLOATFARM
NEXT GENERATION FLOATING WIND FARMS

DELIVERABLE D2.1

High fidelity structural modelling for
identification of critical strain points

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2025-10-29

Document Track Information

Project information	
Project title	Developing the Next Generation of Environmentally-Friendly Floating Wind Farms with Innovative Technologies and Sustainable Solutions
Starting date	01.01.2024
Duration	48 months
Programme	HORIZON EUROPE
Call identifier	HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-01
Grant Agreement No	101136091

Deliverable information	
Deliverable number	D2.1
Work package number	WP2
Deliverable title	High fidelity structural modelling for identification of critical strain points
Lead beneficiary	Ghent University
Author	Songhan Zhang, Kris Hectors, Wim De Waele
Due date	2025-06-30
Actual submission date	2025-06-30
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination level	Public

Revision information			
Version	Contributors	Date	Description
v0.1	Songhan Zhang (Ghent University) Kris Hectors (Ghent University) Wim De Waele (Ghent University)	16.06.2025	First draft
v0.2	Liselotte Ulvgård (Hagnesia)	24.06.2025	Review
v1.0	Songhan Zhang (Ghent University) Kris Hectors (Ghent University)	26.06.2025	Final version
	Wim De Waele (Ghent University)		
v1.1	Songhan Zhang (Ghent University)	27.10.2025	Corrected disclaimer

List of acronyms	
Acronym	Full name
AWS	American Welding Society
DNV	Det Norske Veritas
DOF	Degree of freedom
FOWT	Floating offshore wind turbine
GUI	Graphical user interface
Hexa27n	27-node quadratic hexahedron element
HSS	Hot-spot structural
MPS	Maximum principal stress
SCF	Stress concentration factor
TNS	Transformed normal stress

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About FLOATFARM

The **FLOATFARM** project is a Research and Innovation Action funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe program. This project is closely linked to the **FLOATECH** project (2020-2023) and aims to bring the technologies developed within FLOATECH to the next level of technological readiness, complementing them with a significant number of new concepts, innovations and methods. **FLOATFARM** aims to significantly advance the maturity and competitiveness of floating offshore wind (FOW) technology by increasing energy production, achieving significant cost reductions within the design and implementation phases, improving offshore wind value chain and supporting EU companies in this growing sector. Additionally, **FLOATFARM** aims to decrease negative environmental impacts on marine life and to enhance the public acceptability of FOW, thereby accelerating the EU energy transition. The **FLOATFARM** consortium is coordinated by the Technische Universität Berlin and is made up of 17 partners spread across 8 countries, each contributing to technology and scientific excellence in the wind energy sector.

The approach of **FLOATFARM** can be broken down into three actions:

1. **Turbine Technology:** Development of innovative technologies and methods for improvements on an individual FOW turbine level,
2. **Farm Technology:** Development, investigation and demonstration of technologies that are applicable to an array of turbines within a FOW farm,
3. **Environmental & Socioeconomic Impacts:** Model development, data collection and scenario analysis of environmental, economic and sociological impacts of FOW farms.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Context within FLOATFARM

This document is the deliverable of the Task 2.1, *High fidelity structural modelling for identification of critical strain points*, under the work package 2 (WP2), *Platform, Mooring, Cabling*, of the FLOATFARM project. The major outcome of this task is the development of the numerical tool HFJOINT for the high-fidelity modeling of welded tubular joints. Through interfacing to QBlade, the developed HFJOINT can support for efficient solid-element modeling (which is complementary with the beam-element modeling in QBlade) as well as the dynamic stress analysis associated with the aero-hydro-elasto coupling response from QBlade simulation output, having potential value for the fatigue assessment of floating offshore wind turbine (FOWT) platforms.

1.2 Research background

The lifetime of offshore floating wind turbines are governed by the fatigue of structural joints [4]. It is therefore important to accurately evaluate the fatigue stresses at the critical joints having high stress concentrations. As shown in Fig. 1, the beam-element models, while allowing for fast computing in dynamic simulations such as the aero-hydro-elasto coupling analysis in QBlade [5], are insufficient for accurately predicting stress fields in the regions near welded joints. Meanwhile, solid-element modeling of structural joints [1] presents significant technical challenges due to complexities in mesh generation (and its quality control), precise load definition, and considerable computational demands.

Figure 1. Demand for high-fidelity solid-element modeling of critical joints for local stress analysis

More importantly, in beam-element models, the detailed geometric features, such as the intersection line between chord and brace and the cross section of the weld,

are not explicitly involved. This requires additional information of the welding features as well as advanced meshing techniques to generate a suitable mesh.

1.3 Motivation of this work

Due to the above limitations, we are motivated to develop a semi-automatic workflow for the solid-element mesh of a welded tubular joint. The intersection lines between chord and brace are analytically formulated, and the weld geometry is referred to the American Welding Society (AWS) standard [2]. The Gaussian integral within the finite element analysis framework is employed to address the load mapping from the beam-element forces to the equivalent nodal forces of the solid elements. To avoid the stress singularity at the weld toe, the linear extrapolation is taken from the Det Norske Veritas (DNV) recommendation [3] to evaluate the hot-spot structural (HSS) stress from the nearby stress field. Given the efficient aero-hydro-elasto coupling simulation QBlade, an interface to QBlade is developed, where the geometric features, beam-element loads and time-history responses can be imported. The dynamic stress fields of welded tubular joints, which can hardly be accurately described from beam-element models, can be efficiently computed from the linear superposition without requiring full transient analysis of solid-element models.

Based on the techniques developed from the above, we have further developed a numerical tool, HFJOINT, for the high-fidelity modeling and fatigue assessment of welded tubular joints, offering a user-friendly approach for geometrical modeling, applying load and boundary conditions, stress field analysis and the computation of stress concentration factors along the weld circumference.

1.4 Outline of this document

The remaining part of this document is organized as follow. In Sec. 2, the modeling and analysis techniques developed from this task, including model creation, load mapping, finite element solver and stress analysis are briefly demonstrated. In Sec. 3, the interface to the QBlade software is presented, with respect to the model information, output response data, as well as the dynamic stress field evaluation from beam-element forces. In Sec. 4, the developed graphical user interface (GUI) is shown, along with the initiation of the documentation webpage and the first beta version. Finally, conclusions are made in Sec. 5. The algorithms and methodologies developed are explained in more detail in our journal paper entitled *HFJOINT: A high-fidelity numerical modeling tool for stress concentration factor analysis of welded tubular joints*, which is attached at the end of this document and has now been submitted to the journal *Advances in Engineering Software*.

2 HIGH-FIDELITY MODELING AND ANALYSIS

In the developed HFJOINT, we provide a semi-automatic work flow for the modeling and analysis of welded tubular joints, including the model creation, load application, boundary condition definition, displacement solver, stress evaluation and the computation of stress concentration factor (SCF). In this chapter, an overview of the implementations will be briefly demonstrated. More detailed descriptions on the developed algorithms and the user guides can be found in our journal paper [6] and documentation webpage [7], respectively.

2.1 Mesh generation

The mesh generation starts from the structured mesh of an elementary joint, which is a T- or Y- joint having a single chord and a single brace connected by a weld. The geometry of the weld is accurately modeled considering the intersection line between chord and brace as well as its cross section which is in accordance with the American Welding Society (AWS) recommendations [2]. The brace and chord are divided into several parts (Fig. 2a), ensuring that each region can be generated from a structured mesh using 27-node quadratic hexahedron (Hexa27n) elements through either Lagrange’s interpolation or transfinite interpolation. Based on this, the entire mesh of the elementary joint can then be created by merging the meshes of the subdivided parts. (Fig. 2b)

Figure 2. High-fidelity model creation of an elementary joint: (a) subdivision strategy; (b) structured mesh generation

In HFJOINT, the geometric feature of an elementary joint is governed by a total number of 28 parameters. Five mandatory parameters including the chord radius R , brace radius r , chord thickness T , brace thickness t and brace intersection angle θ must be provided from the users. The remaining parameters are optional, which can either be defined from the user or be automatically computed by default.

After creating the elementary joints, the geometric transforms including translational moving, 3D rotation and symmetric mapping (Fig. 3) can be applied in order to place the elementary joint at the expected position and orientation.

Figure 3. Geometric transforms of an elementary joint: (a) translational moving; (b) 3D rotation; (c) symmetric mapping

The assembling of multiple elementary joints (after geometric transform) allows for the modeling of more complex joints, e.g., the three-brace joint shown in Fig. 4. If necessary, the users can specify a few parts to be excluded. For example, the C-EXT-Zn and C-EXT-Zp are excluded for the elementary joint shown in Fig. 4a.

Figure 4. Modeling of a three-brace joint: (a) structured mesh of the elementary joint; (b) entire mesh after assembling three elementary joints

The geometric information (e.g., values of the mandatory and optional parameters, local/global coordinates of the mesh nodes) of the elementary joint is included in the class 'ElementaryJoint'. The finite element information (e.g., the nodal coordinates and element connectivities) of the entire joint model is included in the class 'FEModel'. The pyvista actors (e.g., nodes, elements and element edges) for the visualization of the finite element model are stored in the class 'ModelPlot'. The created objects can be saved as .pkl files for reuse and update.

2.2 Load mapping

For a created model, the external loads are stored in the global nodal force vector, following the convention of finite element analysis. In HFJOINT, particularly, a group of load-mapping algorithms are developed, which allows to convert the beam-element forces (including axial tension (Fig. 5a), shear force (Fig. 5b), torque (Fig. 5c), bending moment (Fig. 5d)) into the solid-element nodal forces.

Figure 5. Load mapping from beam-element forces to solid-element nodal forces: (a) axial tension; (b) shear force; (c) torque; (d) bending moment

In such cases, the users need to specify the loaded cross section by providing the coordinates of a reference point, the direction of a normal unit vector and the value of the beam-element force. The solid-element nodal forces will then be automatically evaluated. Apart from this, the users are allowed to freely add extra nodal forces for the linear superposition of multiple loads. After evaluated, the nodal force vector can be passed into the class 'ModelPlot' for a visualization as shown in Fig. 5.

2.3 Boundary conditions

Based on the finite element model (i.e., stiffness matrix and external force vector), the boundary conditions are formulated with the Lagrange's equation of the second kind, which allows for fixed/imposed displacements and couplings between multiple degrees-of-freedom (DOFs). For the fixed/imposed displacements, the entry of DOF and the displacement value (zero for fixed case and non-zero value for imposed case) should be specified for each constraint. Such entries can be automatically found if the cross section is selected from a specified reference point and the normal unit vector. The value of each nodal displacement can also be automatically computed if the displacement (e.g., axial/shear/bending deformation) of the corresponding beam-element node can be provided.

Figure 6. Example of a K joint subjected to fixed constraints and imposed displacements

For the coupling between DOFs, the entries of master and slave DOFs as well as the linear relationship factor α yielding in $u_r = \alpha u_m$ should be specified for each coupling. This can be useful for handling more complex cases, such as the hinged/rigid connection between two models and the inclined sliding supports.

2.4 Finite element solver

In HFJOINT, the global stiffness matrix is stored in form of the 'csr' sparse matrix (provided in 'scipy' package), supporting for small memory cost and efficient computation in solving nodal displacements. Afterwards, the stress tensors are first evaluated at the Gaussian quadrature points, and the nodal stresses are then obtained from a quadratic extrapolation. Average stress values are computed for the nodes shared between multiple elements. Finally, the stress field (including normal stresses, shear stresses and von Mises stresses) over the entire model is obtained. The solved nodal displacements and stresses can be passed into the object 'ModelPlot' for a visualization. A scale factor can be applied to amplify the deformation in order to be visible. An example is shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 7. The deformation (scaled) and von Mises stress field of an example three-brace joint subjected to an in-plane bending load

Based on the nodal stresses, the stress at an arbitrary location can be evaluated. As long as the user has specified the coordinate $P(x, y, z)$, the element containing the point as well as its natural coordinates (ξ, η, ζ) will be found (Fig. 8a). The stress at the specified point will then be computed from an interpolation within the element. If the point is outside the domain of the model, a warning message will be given and the computation will be terminated (Fig. 8b).

When extracting the local stress, a slight extrapolation outside the target element is allowed with the tolerance (0.05 by default for the natural coordinates outside $[-1.0, 1.0]$ and can be specified by the user if needed). In such case, the local stress can still be returned even though the specified point is slightly outside but is very much close to the surface of the model.

Figure 8. Identification of the specified point location for element stress interpolation: (a) within the model domain; (2) outside the model domain

2.5 HSS stress & SCFs

After solving the stress field, the HSS stress at the weld toe can be evaluated from the linear extrapolation following the DNV-RP-C203 standard [3]. Based on Sec. 2.4, two local stress tensors are computed from the extrapolation points at certain distances away from the weld toe (Fig. 9a), where the location of the weld toe and the direction vector pointing outside the weld circumference are taken from the 'ElementaryJoint' object. A coordinate transform is then performed to obtain the normal stress along the direction towards the weld toe (Fig. 9b). Apart from this, the maximum principal stress, which is the maximum eigenvalue of the stress tensor, can also be computed.

Figure 9. Evaluation of HSS stress at the weld toe: (a) linear extrapolation; (b) coordinate transform of the stress tensor

The HSS stress at the weld toe is then evaluated from the linear extrapolation based on either the transformed normal stress or the maximum principal stress.

For a welded tubular joint, the HSS stress can be evaluated along the weld circumference at both the brace side and the chord side. The SCF can then be obtained by computing the ratio between the HSS and the nominal stress (an axial or bending stress resulting from the corresponding beam model). Taking a X joint (Fig. 10a) for example, a pair of axial tensions is symmetrically applied on the braces. The nodal displacements and stress field can then be solved from a half-model as shown in Fig. 10b where symmetric boundary condition is applied at the bottom side.

Figure 10. Stress field of the example X joint: (a) boundary and load conditions; (b) stress field solved from the half model

Considering both the transformed normal stress (TNS) and the maximum principal stress (MPS), the evaluated SCFs are shown in Fig. 11.

Figure 11. The SCFs along the weld circumference: (a) brace side; (b) chord side

3 INTERFACE TO QBLADE

In order to deliver a user-friendly approach for the high-fidelity modeling of the joints in floating wind turbine platforms, an interface to QBlade has been initiated, where the geometric features can be imported from the beam-element model defined in the QBlade .str file, and the load information can be obtained from the QBlade simulation output file. The data is stored and processed in the class 'QBModel'.

3.1 Model information

The structural information is automatically extracted from the .str file specified by the user. As demonstrated in Fig. 12, the data sets under the titles 'SUBELEMENTS-RIGID', 'SUBELEMENTSRIGID_RECT', 'SUBJOINTS', 'SUBCONSTRAINTS', 'SUBMEMBERS', 'MOORELEMENTS', 'MOORMEMBERS' and 'SUBELEMENTS' are extracted and are reformed into python lists. The imported model information is stored under the keyword 'substr' within the 'QBModel' class.

Figure 12. Structural data imported from QBlade to HFJOINT

The imported model can be visualized in HFJOINT, showing the global coordinate system, model geometry, joint ID, joint node, member ID and member axis. A few typical examples are shown in Fig. 13

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 13. Examples of model imports from QBlade to HFJOINT: (a) NREL 5MW OC4 Semisub; (b) NREL/MIT 5MW TLP; (c) IEA 15MW VolturUS-S

It should be noted that, in QBlade .str file, the thickness of cylindrical shell members and the local coordinate system of the beam members are not explicitly provided. However, these are quite important for the solid-element modeling and the load mapping in HFJOINT. Given this fact, we have developed an iterative algorithm which solves the wall thickness from the bending stiffness (EI) and axial stiffness (EA) which are available in the .str file. Also, the local coordinate systems of the beam members are reproduced in HFJOINT following the convention of QBlade.

Figure 14. The thickness of the thin-wall cylindrical members and the local coordinate systems of the beam members reproduced from the HFJOINT interface

A typical example for the 'NREL 5MW OC4 Semisub' model is shown in Fig. 14, where the solved thickness is visualized and the local coordinate systems are shown at the mid position of each member. The local x , y and z axes are denoted by the short lines with red, green and blue colors, respectively.

Based on this interface, the users can effortlessly create the high-fidelity solid-element model of a joint. Once the IDs of the chord and brace members are specified, the mandatory parameters are automatically fetched from the 'QBModel' object. Since the coordinate of the joint center can be identified, translational moving and 3D rotation are automatically applied to ensure that the solid-element model is perfectly consistent with the beam-element model created in QBlade, as shown in Fig. 15.

Figure 15. The high-fidelity solid-element model of the three-brace joint created from the QBlade-HFJOINT interface

3.2 Simulation output

From the developed interface, the QBlade simulation output can also be passed into the HFJOINT tool as long as the .txt file is specified by the user. The work flow is shown in Fig. 16.

Figure 16. Simulation output data imported from QBlade to HFJOINT

For each output variable, the name is used as the key value, and the time-history responses is converted as a numpy vector.

3.3 Dynamic stress field

From a QBlade simulation, the time-history responses, e.g., the beam-element forces and nodal displacements, are obtained as mentioned in Sec. 3.2. Based on these beam-element forces, the dynamic stress field of the welded tubular joint can then be analyzed from the high-fidelity model, as shown in Fig. 17.

Figure 17. Evaluation of the dynamic stress field in a high-fidelity tubular joint model based QBlade simulation output

Associated with each of the beam-element force (axial tension, in-plane-/out-of-plane shear, torque, in-plane-/out-of-plane bending for each node), a fundamental solution, i.e., the displacement and stress field resulting from a unit load, can be solved from HFJOINT. At each time point, the force amplitudes extracted from the QBlade-HFJOINT interface are applied as the weight factors. The overall stress field is then computed from the linear superposition of the fundamental solutions. Similarly, the dynamic nodal displacements (characterizing the overall dynamic deformation of the joint) can also be evaluated from such linear superposition.

The computed dynamic stress and displacement are finally stored in a 2D numpy array where the row and column entries indicate the node ID and time point, respectively. The users can either plot the 3D stress field of the joint at a specified time point (e.g., Fig. 18a) or plot the time-history of the dynamic stress response at a specified location (e.g. Fig. 18b).

(b)

Figure 18. Dynamic stress of the three-brace joint evaluated from the HFJOINT solid-element model: (a) stress field at a certain time point; (b) time-history of the von Mises stress at a specified location

It can be seen from Fig. 18 that the braces are bended downward and are dominated by tensile stress. This is because the main column (i.e., the chord) is pushing upwards by the buoyancy force while the braces are pulling downwards (and also outward) by the mooring cables.

4 GRAPHICAL USER INTERFACE

Since the development of HFJOINT version 0.1.0, we have included a graphical user interface (GUI), allowing the users, especially for non-expert users, to perform the high-fidelity numerical modeling and stress concentration analysis for welded tubular joints.

4.1 Documentation webpage

A documentation webpage has been initiated and is available online [7]. The first page and the outline are shown in Fig. 19.

Figure 19. Documentation webpage of the HFJOINT tool

The main contents of this webpage remain in development, but will be completed soon. The webpage will be periodically updated along with the technical improvements of the HFJOINT.

4.2 First beta version

Based on the main features demonstrated in Sec. 2 and Sec. 3, we have created our first beta version. The program is compiled into an executable (.exe) file, which can be easily launched by simply double clicking without requiring any installation procedure. The download link will soon be available on the documentation webpage. The GUI is split into two parts. The left part involving five tab panels is used for the inputs and outputs. The right part is used for the visualization. A brief overview for each tab panel is given below.

The first tab panel is 'Create model'. The users are required to provide the mandatory parameters, while the optional parameters and geometric transforms are optional. The users can specify the names of the parts to be excluded during the modeling. The elementary joint can then be created and saved as a .pkl file. After creating multiple joints, the complex joint can be generated by importing multiple elementary joint files. A few typical joints can be directly generated from 'fast modeling' panel.

Figure 20. HFJOINT GUI: Model creation

The second tab panel is 'Interface to QBlade'. After selecting the QBlade substructure model file (.str) and the simulation output file (.txt), the involved information will be imported by clicking the 'Import QBlade model' bottom. If the QBlade model consists of 'SUBELEMENTS', the wall thickness can be automatically calculated by clicking the bottom 'Solve wall thickness', and in the model creation, the mandatory parameters can then be specified as the ID of the QBlade member, e.g., 'Brace radius': M_24, 'Chord radius': M_1. All the response output variables are collected in the pull list below. The time-history curves can be shown immediately once a variable is selected from the pull list.

Select QBlade files
Import model

Visualization
Find wall thickness

Plot simulated response

Figure 21. HFJOINT GUI: Interface to QBlade

The third tab panel is 'Define load'. This tab panel can be operated after the model creation, but the model files (including elementary joint and FE model files) must be imported if the tool is restarted. If the model is imported from QBlade, the load parameters will be automatically filled as long as the member ID, type of the beam force and the force amplitude are provided.

Import model files

Load parameters

Automatic fill

Visualization

Figure 22. HFJOINT GUI: Load definition

The fourth tab panel is 'Solver'. Three approaches are available for the definition of boundary conditions. The first approach allows to fix all the nodes on a cross section specified by a reference point and a normal vector. The second approach supports to fix the selected DOFs of a group of selected nodes. The third approach

is to directly fix the nodes at the ends of the chord. After clicking the 'Solve' button, the displacement and stress will be evaluated. The deformation (with a specified amplification factor) and the von Mises stress field can be visualized. The solved displacement and stress values will be updated into the 'FEModel' object and can be exported as a '.pkl' file.

- Approach I
- Approach II
- Approach III
- Solve
 - ✓ nodal displacements
 - ✓ nodal stress tensor
 - ✓ von Mises stresses
- Show stress field & deformation

Figure 23. HFJOINT GUI: Finite element solver

The last tab panel is 'SCFs'. The users need to specify the loaded member ID (i.e., the loaded brace), the side (chord or brace) of interest and the stress type (transformed normal stress or maximum principle stress). The SCFs along the weld circumference will be plotted, and the data can be exported as a '.txt' file.

- Import model files
- Select options
- Export SCF data
- Plot SCF curve

Figure 24. HFJOINT GUI: SCF computation

5 CONCLUSIONS

1. The developed HFJOINT numerical tool provides a semi-automatic and user-friendly approach for the high-fidelity modeling of welded tubular joints, offering structured mesh generation, automated load mapping, boundary condition definition, in-house finite element solver and stress field evaluation. This can support for more accurate fatigue assessment compared to traditional beam-element models.
2. Within the HFJOINT tool, an interface to QBlade is included, enabling seamless importing the geometric features and simulation outputs from QBlade beam-element models into HFJOINT high-fidelity solid-element models. From the dynamic beam-element forces from QBlade simulation, the dynamic stress field of the joint can be evaluated from the superposition of fundamental solutions.
3. Advanced computational techniques are applied in HFJOINT, such as the transfinite interpolation for creating perfect structured mesh, the 27-node quadratic hexahedron (Hexa27n) element (which is a complete Lagrange's element), load mapping from surface traction (resulting from beam-element force) to equivalent solid-element nodal forces. These help to ensure the accuracy and efficiency of the high-fidelity models.
4. A graphical user interface has been developed, along with the HFJOINT documentation webpage. This enables both expert and non-expert users to effortlessly perform the high-fidelity numerical modeling and stress concentration factor analysis of welded tubular joints. The developed functions are extensible to handle more complex cases and will be periodically updated in the future.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Ahmadi and A. Z. Nejad. "Geometrical effects on the local joint flexibility of two-planar tubular DK-joints in jacket substructure of offshore wind turbines under OPB loading." In: *Thin-Walled Structures* 114 (2017), pp. 122–133.
- [2] AWS. *D1.1/D1.1M:2025 - Structural Welding Code - Steel*. American Welding Society, 2025.
- [3] DNV. *DNV-RP-C203: Fatigue design of offshore steel structures - Recommended practice (Edition 2024-10)*. Det Norske Veritas (DNV): Oslo, Norway, 2024.
- [4] D. Haselibozechaloe, J. Correia, P Mendes, A. de Jesus, and F Berto. "A review of fatigue damage assessment in offshore wind turbine support structure." In: *International Journal of Fatigue* 164 (2022), p. 107145.
- [5] D. Marten, J. Wendler, G. Pechlivanoglou, C. N. Nayeri, and C. O. Paschereit. "QBLADE: an open source tool for design and simulation of horizontal and vertical axis wind turbines." In: *International Journal of Emerging Technology and Advanced Engineering* 3.3 (2013), pp. 264–269.
- [6] S. H. Zhang, W. De Waele, and K. Hectors. "HFJOINT: A high-fidelity numerical modeling tool for stress concentration factor analysis of welded tubular joints." In: *Advances in Engineering Software* (ready to submit).
- [7] S. H. Zhang, K. Hectors, and W. De Waele. *HFJOINT - Documentation and user guidelines*. 2025. URL: <https://github.ugent.be/pages/SOZHANG/mytool-docs/> (visited on 06/06/2025).

Appendix

A JOURNAL PAPER

The journal paper *Hfjoint: A High-Fidelity Numerical Modeling Tool for Stress Concentration Factor Analysis of Welded Tubular Joints* is submitted to the journal *Advances in Engineering Software*, and is now under review. The preprint has been available on the SSRN website (click [here](#) to visit). The suggested citation information is as below:

Zhang, Songhan and De Waele, Wim and Hectors, Kris. *HFjoint: A High-Fidelity Numerical Modeling Tool for Stress Concentration Factor Analysis of Welded Tubular Joints*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5309685>

The fulltext of the preprint is attached in the following of this report.

HFJOINT: A high-fidelity numerical modeling tool for stress concentration factor analysis of welded tubular joints

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Abstract

Assessing the fatigue performance of welded tubular joints is crucial to the safety and durability of their host structures. Fast-computing beam-element models are insufficient to accurately capture local stress concentrations at the intersection region, leading to inaccurate lifetime predictions. In this work, a high-fidelity numerical modeling tool, HFJOINT, is developed for stress concentration analysis of welded tubular joints, following a flexible and user-friendly process. The work flow begins with the creation of an elementary T/Y-joint using quadratic hexahedron elements, where the weld geometry is generated in accordance with the American Welding Society (AWS) standard. The chord and brace are divided into several regions allowing for an entirely structured mesh. The geometric transformations (translation, rotation and symmetric) of multiple elementary joints support for creating more complex joints. After evaluating the stiffness matrix, the beam-element forces are converted to external tractions acting on the loaded cross section, and are then transformed into solid-element nodal forces from the Gaussian integral. The boundary conditions are defined from the geometric constraints formulated by the Lagrange's equation of the second kind. Based on the solved displacement vector, the postprocessing module enables to evaluate the local stress at any specified point. Using linear extrapolation, the hot-spot structural stress and the stress concentration factors (SCFs) along the weld circumference are finally computed. The developed tool is verified by comparing with the SCFs of benchmark T-, K- and X- joint models, showing its potential for fatigue analysis of welded tubular joints in broad practical applications.

Keywords: welded tubular joint, finite element analysis, structured mesh, load mapping, hot-spot stress

1 Nomenclature

2	$\bar{\sigma}$	The normal stress on a specified 3D plane after coordinate transform of stress tensor
3	σ	Stress tensor in the vector form
4	η	The 2nd natural coordinate for Lagrange's or transfinite interpolation
5	$\vec{\mathbf{r}}$	Local coordinates of an interpolation point in the weld cross section
6	ϕ_r	Rodrigues' rotation angle of the 3D rotation about a specified axis
7	ϕ_w	The slope angle of the weld upper surface
8	Ψ	Dihedral angle between the chord and brace walls
9	ψ_r	Euler angle for the 3D rotation about global Z axis
10	ρ	Polar angle of the weld circumference
11	σ	Normal stress (having the subscripts xx, yy and zz)

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12	σ_{HS}	Hot spot stress at the weld toe
13	σ_{nm}	Nominal stress evaluated from a beam member
14	τ	Shear stress (having the subscripts xy, yz and xz)
15	\mathbf{A}^e	Boolean matrix mapping the element DOFs into the global DOFs list
16	\mathbf{B}	Element strain matrix
17	\mathbf{D}	Constitutive matrix of the material
18	\mathbf{F}	Global nodal force vector
19	\mathbf{f}	Surface traction field resulting from beam element load
20	\mathbf{J}	Jacobian matrix from natural coordinates to the physical coordinates
21	\mathbf{K}	Global stiffness matrix
22	\mathbf{K}_e	Element stiffness matrix
23	\mathbf{R}	Coordinate transformation matrix
24	\mathbf{U}	Global nodal displacement vector
25	\mathbf{U}_e	Element nodal displacement vector
26	\mathbf{U}_F	The displacement vector of the DOFs to be solve
27	\mathbf{U}_{im}	The global imposed displacement vector
28	\mathbf{U}_I	The displacement vector of the imposed DOFs
29	θ	brace intersection angle
30	θ_r	Euler angle for the 3D rotation about global Y axis
31	φ_r	Euler angle for the 3D rotation about global X axis
32	\vec{e}_j	The unit direction vectors for the local coordinate system of the weld cross section ($j = 1, 2, 3$)
33	\vec{n}	Normal unit vector of a reference plane
34	\vec{r}_0	The global coordinates of a given point at the top surface of the weld.
35	$\vec{r}_{[...]}$	Global coordinates of the points in a transfinite mesh, where the subscripts T/B/L/R denotes top/bottom/left/right edges, respectively, and the subscripts 1/2/3/4 denotes the corner nodes
36		
37	\vec{r}_{cb}	Global coordinates of the points at the inner surface of the chord
38	\vec{r}_{ct}	Global coordinates of the points at the outer surface of the chord
39	\vec{r}_c	Global coordinates of the node at the reference plane of the brace
40	\vec{r}_{ht}	Global coordinates of the points at the interface between B-HS and B-TR regions
41	\vec{r}_{I_1}	Intersection line between chord and brace (inner side)
42	\vec{r}_{I_2}	Intersection line between chord and brace (outer side)
43	\vec{r}_I	Intersection line between two cylinders (outer side)
44	\vec{r}_{mi}	Global coordinate of a point symmetric about a specified reference plane
45	\vec{r}_{mv}	Global coordinate of a point after 3D rotation
46	\vec{r}_{mv}	Global coordinate of a point after translational moving
47	\vec{r}_t	Global coordinates of the points at the top of the B-UN region
48	\vec{r}_v	A vector containing the coordinate of the weld vertices
49	\vec{r}_{w0}	The global coordinates of the inner intersection point (I_1) of the weld cross section
50	\vec{r}_{ij}	Coordinates of the weld interpolation points in the local coordinate system

51	ξ	The 1st natural coordinate for Lagrange's or transfinite interpolation
52	Ξ_j	A geometry sequence for a transition mesh where the element sizes gradually change.
53	ζ	The 3rd natural coordinate for Lagrange's or transfinite interpolation
54	A	Area of the cross section
55	b_{cts}	Width of the chord transition region
56	F_{ax}	Axial force applied on a beam member
57	F_{ips}	In-plane shear force applied on a beam member
58	F_{ops}	Out-of-plane shear force applied on a beam member
59	I	Moment of inertia of the cross section
60	L	Total length of the chord
61	L_{bu}	The axial length of the B-UN region
62	L_h	The distance from the joint center to the reference plane of the brace
63	M_{ipb}	In-plane bending moment applied on a beam member
64	M_{opb}	Out-of-plane bending moment applied on a beam member
65	N_j	The bilinear interpolation functions for the mesh grid of weld cross section ($j = 1, 2, 3, 4$)
66	n_{bhs}	Number of elements along the axis of the brace hot-spot region
67	n_e	Total number of elements in a finite element mesh
68	n_n	Total number of nodes in a finite element mesh
69	q	The factor describing the steepness of the changing element sizes in a transition mesh.
70	R	Outer radius of the chord cross section
71	r	Outer radius of the brace cross section
72	R_w	The gap in height between the chord and brace
73	T_b	Torsional moment applied on a beam member
74	t_w	The thickness of the weld cross section
75	w	Weight factors for the Gaussian numerical integral
76	x_j	The distance from the stress extrapolation point to the weld toe ($j = 1, 2$)
77	y_c	Distance from a specified point to the neutral surface

78 1. Introduction

79 Tubular joints with welded connections are used in a variety of complex, large-scale structures such as
 80 offshore wind turbines Saini et al. (2016) and bridges Udomworarat et al. (2002), because of the balance
 81 between strength, own weight and ease of fabrication. As shown in Fig. 1, the simplest case of a welded
 82 tubular joint consists of a single brace and chord connecting at a certain intersection angle. The cross
 83 section of the weld depends on the dihedral angle, which varies along the weld circumference, reaching its
 84 maximum at the crown and the minimum at the saddle. The lifetime of welded tubular structures is usually
 85 governed by the fatigue life of the tubular joints because of the stress concentration near the welds Becker
 86 et al. (1972). Fatigue experiments on large tubular joints are extremely costly. High-fidelity numerical
 87 modeling techniques N'diaye et al. (2009) provide more accurate, efficient and versatile approaches for the
 88 fatigue assessment of tubular joints, but require expertise and are time intensive when a generalized modeling
 89 approach is considered.

Figure 1: Geometric features of a representative welded tubular joint: (a) overview of the joint; (b) close-up view at the intersection between brace and chord walls.

90 The numerical modeling of tubular joints has been an active field of research for several decades Lee (1999).
 91 For complex structures consisting of a large number of tubular members, global models are conventionally
 92 developed using beam elements Chen and Zhang (1996); Sandal et al. (2018). Such low-fidelity models are
 93 computationally efficient, but are insufficient to accurately describe the local stress fields near the welds that
 94 govern the fatigue life. To address the limitation of beam models, shell-element models Vigh and Dunai
 95 (2004); Zheng et al. (2024) have been introduced, where the geometric features of the tubular walls and
 96 their intersection area are presented. However, these models introduce stress singularities at the sharp edges,
 97 leading to highly overestimated fatigue stresses. For this reason, the surface stress extrapolation hot-spot
 98 structural (HSS) stress approach was proposed to evaluate the stress at the weld toe from the extrapolation
 99 of nearby local nodal stresses. To make the trade off between a beam model (computationally efficient) and
 100 a shell model (accurate), the stress concentration factor (SCF) Marshall (2013), characterizing the ratio
 101 between the shell HSS stress and the beam nominal stress, is used. In engineering design, the SCFs are
 102 determined from empirical parametric equations that are fitted to simulation data and validated with limited
 103 experiment data. Therefore, these parametric equations have inherent limitations. Due to the involved
 104 exponential functions, the accuracy of the formulae is significantly reduced when a part of the parameters
 105 are outside their feasible scopes. With increasing computation power, high-fidelity solid-element modeling
 106 offers a robust solution for exactly taken into account the complex geometries of tubular joints Hectors and
 107 De Waele (2020); Woghiren and Brennan (2009); Zavvar et al. (2021). This allows for the consideration of
 108 the detailed shape of the weld cross-section, for example based on the American Welding Society (AWS)
 109 standard AWS (2025). Such high-fidelity models typically use 8-node linear Vignesh Chellappan and
 110 Nallayarasu (2019) or 20-node quadratic hexahedron Hectors and De Waele (2020) elements which are
 111 available in commercial finite element software packages like Abaqus Qian et al. (2002), Ansys Li et al.
 112 (2014) and Comsol Hasan et al. (2024). In most cases, a linear-element mesh is generated, namely the raw
 113 mesh Lie et al. (2003), and is then upgraded to a 20-node quadratic-element mesh, where the added edge
 114 nodes are conventionally assumed at the middle positions. High-fidelity modeling in fatigue assessments of
 115 welded tubular joints presents several challenges that remain to be addressed:

- 116 (i) Mesh quality control. Due to the complex geometry, non-structured meshes are usually considered for
 117 the sake of convenience and adaptivity. This may, however, result in distorted elements which affect
 118 the precision of computation. A fine, high-quality mesh near the weld is required in order to capture
 119 the high stress gradient and related stress concentration Lee et al. (2010). Conversely, the global

120 mesh size should ideally be relatively coarse in order to limit the computational cost. This further
121 increases the difficulty in mesh quality control. An alternative approach is to divide the joint into a
122 number of simpler pieces, ensuring that a tailored structured mesh is possible for each of the pieces Lie
123 et al. (2003). The meshed pieces are then merged to form a meshed representation of the entire joint.
124 However, a complex transition scheme remains needed to connect the fine mesh zone near the weld and
125 the far-field zone having a coarser mesh, especially for the compatibility along the thickness direction.

- 126 (ii) Trade off between accuracy and computational efficiency. The 8-node linear hexahedron and 20-node
127 serendipity hexahedron (where the cross terms are omitted from its shape functions) elements provided
128 in most softwares are insufficient to present the internal stress gradient without a very refined mesh.
129 The complete quadratic hexahedron element has higher accuracy in describing large stress gradients,
130 having potential in handling stress-concentration problems Oberrecht et al. (2014), but a larger number
131 of DOFs have to be included.
- 132 (iii) Complicated workflow. The SCF analysis of a welded tubular joint involves multiple steps including
133 geometric modeling Li et al. (2024), mesh generation, load definition, static solver and surface stress
134 extrapolated HSS stress determination. These refer to the interaction between multiple software tools
135 and considerable manual interventions, which are challenging to handle, especially for non-expert users.

136 It can be concluded that most modeling techniques are limited in accurately capturing the weld geometry,
137 creating a high-quality mesh and performing a stress concentration analysis. To address these challenges,
138 a structured mesh strategy based on 27-node completely quadratic hexahedron elements (Hexa27n), along
139 with the solver for evaluating the stress field and SCFs, is proposed in the present work. It allows for the
140 numerical modeling and fatigue assessment of welded tubular joints using a semi-automatic, user-friendly and
141 controllable approach. In the proposed mesh strategy, a joint is always modeled from the integration of one
142 or multiple T/Y-joints (which is called elementary joints in the following). Such elementary joint is divided
143 into a number of interconnecting regions. Some regions are further divided into a number of parts allowing
144 for structured mesh through either linear or transfinite interpolation in the 3D space. The high-fidelity
145 model of the elementary joint is then obtained by merging the structured Hexa27n meshes of all parts. This
146 supports the modeling of more complex multi-brace, multi-planar tubular joints by creating, transforming
147 and merging multiple elementary joints. By considering the boundary conditions from geometric constraints
148 and element surface tractions (e.g., the distributed stress converted from beam-element forces), the stress
149 field of the joint can be solved, allowing for the evaluation of hot-spot stresses and stress concentration
150 factors along the full circumference of the weld. The proposed methodology has been integrated into a
151 novel tool called 'high-fidelity numerical modeling of welded tubular joints (HFJOINT)'. The tool presents a
152 user-friendly interface for (semi)-automatic generation of Hexa27n models of welded tubular joints, allowing
153 engineers to accurately perform SCF calculations for a variety of actual joint geometries without being
154 affected by the validity limitations of empirical formulae.

155 The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. The high-fidelity model generation of an elementary
156 joint is demonstrated in Sec. 2. Based on the geometric transformations of elementary joints, the modeling
157 of complex joints is illustrated in Sec. 3. The finite element formulation, involving the stiffness matrix,
158 geometric constraints, the force vector and the evaluations of stress field and SCFs, is derived in Sec. 4.
159 The SCFs evaluated from the developed HFJOINT are verified by means of case studies in Sec. 5, including
160 a benchmark T-joint model for mesh refinement, computational cost and accuracy, as well as both X- and
161 K-joints for comparison with experiment data. Finally, conclusions are made in Sec. 6

162 2. Structured mesh of an elementary joint

163 In this section, the mesh generation of an elementary joint (i.e., a T- or Y-joint having a single pair of chord
164 and brace) will be demonstrated. First of all, a subdivision with respect to the member, region and part
165 levels, is applied on the elementary joint (Fig. 2) in order to cope with the geometric complexity.

Figure 2: Subdivision strategy of an elementary joint in terms of member, region and part levels.

166 In HFJOINT convention, the elementary joint is partitioned into brace, weld and chord members. The brace
 167 is divided into the hot-spot region (B-HS) having a refined mesh, the uniform region (B-UN) having a coarser
 168 mesh and the transition region (B-TR) where the mesh size is gradually varying. The chord is divided into
 169 the plug region (C-PL) at the center, the hot-spot region (C-HS) below the weld, the transition region
 170 (C-TR) having an edge varying from circle-like to quadrilateral-like, and the extend region (C-EXT). The
 171 C-PL region is further divided into the center part (C-PL-CT) and the transition part (C-PL-TR). The C-
 172 EXT region is further divided into four parts towards the X-negative (C-EXT-Xn), X-positive (C-EXT-Xp),
 173 Z-negative (C-EXT-Zn), and Z-positive (C-EXT-Zp) directions. Based on this strategy, each destination
 174 (part/region) can always be modeled from a perfect structured mesh using hexahedron elements.

Figure 3: The 27-node quadratic hexahedron element used in HFJOINT: (a) an example in the global coordinate system; (b) ordering of the nodes in the natural coordinate system.

175 Considering the accuracy, adaptability and computational efficiency, a complete Lagrange's 27-node quadratic
 176 hexahedron (Hexa27n) element (Fig. 3), is developed and is employed by default in HFJOINT. The conven-
 177 tion of the node numbering and the natural coordinates of the nodes are listed in Tab. A.5. The structured
 178 mesh for each region/part will be demonstrated next.

179 2.1. Weld

180 In order to properly locate the discretized weld cross sections, the global coordinate system (GCS) (X-Y-Z
 181 in Fig. 4(a)) is defined to describe the geometry of the entire joint. The center of the GCS is placed at the
 182 intersection point of the chord-brace axes. The X-axis is parallel with the central axis of the chord. The
 183 Y-axis is inside the plane of the chord-brace axes and is meantime perpendicular to the X-axis. The Z-axis
 184 (out-of-plane) can then be determined by the right-hand rule. In the GCS, the overall geometric shape of
 185 the weld is governed by the intersection lines I_1 (between the inner surface of the brace and the outer surface
 186 of the chord) and I_2 (between the outer surface of the brace and the outer surface of the chord).

Figure 4: Geometric profile of the weld: (a) position and orientation in the global coordinate system; (b) shape of the cross-section in the local coordinate system

187 To describe the position of a weld cross-section, the polar angle ρ is defined where $\rho = 0$ indicates the crown
 188 at the positive X-side (recall Fig. 1(a)) and ρ increases with the rotation about the global Y-axis. The outer
 189 intersection line between two cylinders having the radius R (chord) and r (brace) can be described by the
 190 parametric function Hector and De Waele (2021):

$$\vec{\mathbf{r}}_1 = \left(\frac{1}{\sin \theta} \left\{ r \sin \rho - \left[R - \sqrt{R^2 - r^2 \cos^2 \rho} \right] \cos \theta \right\}, \sqrt{R^2 - r^2 \cos^2 \rho}, r \cos \rho \right) \quad (1)$$

191 where θ is the brace intersection angle which has been denoted in Fig. 1(a). At each polar angle, a local
 192 coordinate system is attached to the weld cross section, see Fig. 4(b). The radial unit vector:

$$\vec{\mathbf{e}}_1 = \frac{\vec{\mathbf{r}}_{I_2} - \vec{\mathbf{r}}_{I_1}}{\|\vec{\mathbf{r}}_{I_2} - \vec{\mathbf{r}}_{I_1}\|} \quad (2)$$

193 is pointing from I_1 to I_2 , where both $\vec{\mathbf{r}}_{I_1}$ and $\vec{\mathbf{r}}_{I_2}$ are evaluated from Eq. 1 but the brace radius r is taken
 194 $r - t$ (where t is the thickness of the brace) and r , respectively. The tangent unit vector:

$$\vec{\mathbf{e}}_2 = \frac{1}{\|d\vec{\mathbf{r}}_{I_1}/d\rho\|} \frac{d\vec{\mathbf{r}}_{I_1}}{d\rho} \quad (3)$$

195 is pointing in the tangent direction of the inner intersection line, where,

$$\frac{d\vec{\mathbf{r}}_1}{d\rho} = \left(\frac{1}{\sin \theta} \left\{ r \cos \rho + \frac{r^2 \sin \rho \cos \rho \cos \theta}{\sqrt{R^2 - r^2 \cos^2 \rho}} \right\}, \frac{r^2 \sin \rho \cos \rho}{\sqrt{R^2 - r^2 \cos^2 \rho}}, -r \sin \rho \right) \quad (4)$$

196 is explicitly derived from Eq. 1 using the chain rule. The upward unit vector:

$$\vec{e}_3 = \vec{e}_1 \times \vec{e}_2 \quad (5)$$

197 is perpendicular to the previous two. The shape of the weld cross-section can then be described within the
 198 planar coordinate $\vec{e}_1 - \vec{e}_3$, as shown with the red and green arrows in Fig. 4(b). In the local coordinate
 199 system of the weld cross-section, a set of geometric relationships governing the shape of the weld cross
 200 section are proposed in the AWS standard D1.1:2025 AWS (2025). For complete joint penetration (CJP)
 201 welds, the detailed cross-section features depend on the dihedral angle Ψ (the spatial angle between \vec{e}_1 and
 202 the brace axis which can be found in Fig. 1(b)), as shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: The geometries of the weld cross-sections Marshall et al. (2013) with respect to the range of the dihedral angle ψ : (a) detail A; (b) detail B blunt (left) and B sharp (right); (c) detail C; (d) transition from C to D; (e) detail D.

203 Within the LCS of the weld cross-section, the geometric dimensions shown in Fig. 5 allow to solve the
 204 the coordinates of the vertices I₂, A, B, C, D and E, based on the original point I₁(0,0). Taking detail B
 205 (Fig. 5(b)) as an example, the coordinates can be calculated from:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{r}_{I_2} &= \left(\frac{t_w}{\sin \psi}, 0 \right), \quad \vec{r}_A = \left(\frac{R_w}{\tan \psi}, 0 \right), \quad \vec{r}_B = \left(\frac{R_w}{\tan \psi}, R_w \right), \quad \vec{r}_C = (0, R_w), \quad \vec{r}_E = \left(h_w + \frac{t_w + F_w}{\sin \psi}, 0 \right) \\ \vec{r}_D &= \left(\frac{t}{\sin \psi} + \frac{\cos \psi (t \tan \phi_w / \sin \psi + R_w)}{\sin \psi - \cos \psi \tan \phi_w}, R_w + \frac{\sin \psi (t \tan \phi_w / \sin \psi + R_w)}{\sin \psi - \cos \psi \tan \phi_w} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

206 where t_w is the thickness of the weld cross section, ϕ_w is the slope angle of the weld upper surface, R_w is the
 207 gap in height between the chord and brace. Since the purpose of the model is to determine the local elastic
 208 stress fields along the brace-chord intersection as input to high-cycle fatigue analyses, the finite element
 209 simulations will be performed considering linear elastic material behavior. It is fair to assume that the
 210 linear elastic material properties of the base and weld material are the same. In that case, only the convex
 211 envelope of the weld cross-section has to be modeled. The weld cross-section can thus be characterized by
 212 the vertices A, B, D and E (Fig. 4(b)). Such cross-section can then be meshed into a structured grid through
 213 the bilinear interpolation:

$$\vec{r}_{ij} = \left(\{N_1, N_2, N_3, N_4\} \Big|_{\xi=\xi_i, \eta=\eta_j} \otimes \mathbf{I}^{2 \times 2} \right) \vec{r}_v \quad (7)$$

214 where the interpolation functions, in terms of discrete (ξ, η) points, are evaluated by:

$$N_1 = \frac{1}{4}(1 - \xi)(1 - \eta) \quad (8)$$

$$N_2 = \frac{1}{4}(1 - \xi)(1 + \eta) \quad (9)$$

$$N_3 = \frac{1}{4}(1 + \xi)(1 - \eta) \quad (10)$$

$$N_4 = \frac{1}{4}(1 + \xi)(1 + \eta) \quad (11)$$

215 and the coordinates of the vertices are collected as:

$$\vec{r}_v = \{x_A, y_A, x_B, y_B, x_D, y_D, x_E, y_E\}^T \quad (12)$$

216 After obtaining the local coordinates of each node, \vec{r} , the positions of the nodes within the global coordinate
 217 system, \vec{r} , can be evaluated through a translational motion (ensuring that the point I_1 is exactly at the
 218 inner intersection point \vec{r}_{w0}) and a 3D rotation (ensuring that all the unit vectors are pointing to the correct
 219 directions). This is implemented by the coordinate transformation:

$$\vec{r} = \vec{r}_{w0} + \mathbf{R}\vec{r} \quad (13)$$

220 where

$$\mathbf{R} = \{\vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_2, \vec{e}_3\}^T \quad (14)$$

221 is the 3D rotation matrix from the global coordinate system to the local coordinate system.

Figure 6: Example of a structured mesh of a tubular joint weld profile using tri-quadratic hexahedron elements ($n_p = 24$, $n_\xi = 1$, $n_\eta = 1$): (a) Global shape of the weld; (b) a close-up view of the weld cross section at $z = 0$ with the unit vectors of the local coordinate system.

222 *2.2. Brace*

223 As mentioned in Fig. 2, the brace is divided into three regions: B-HS (hot-spot region), B-TR (transition
 224 region) and B-UN (uniformly meshed region). For the sake of convenience, a reference plane containing the
 225 interface between the B-TR and B-UN regions is defined by its normal vector $\vec{n} = (\cos \theta, \sin \theta, 0)$ and the
 226 point at the center of the cross section $\vec{r}_c = (x_c, y_c, z_c)$ (Fig. 7).

Figure 7: Node mapping from the top surface of the weld to the reference plane at the top surface of the transition region

227 For each node at the top surface of the weld, denoted by $\vec{r}_0 = (x_0, y_0, z_0)$, the corresponding node at the
 228 reference plane is:

$$\vec{r}_c = \vec{r}_0 + (L - x_0 \cos \theta - y_0 \sin \theta) \vec{n} \quad (15)$$

229 In addition to the reference plane, the nodes at the interface between the B-HS and B-TR regions, \vec{r}_{ht} , as
 230 well as the nodes at the top surface of the B-UN region, \vec{r}_t , are:

$$\vec{r}_{ht} = \vec{r}_0 + L_h \vec{n} \quad (16)$$

$$\vec{r}_t = \vec{r}_c + L_{bu} \vec{n} \quad (17)$$

231 where L_h is the distance between the joint center (i.e., the origin of the global coordinate system) and the
 232 center of the reference plane, and L_{bu} is the axial length of the B-UN region. Based on this, the nodes
 233 within the B-HS region and B-UN region can be obtained from uniform interpolations between \vec{r}_0 and \vec{r}_{ht} ,
 234 and between \vec{r}_c and \vec{r}_t , respectively. The nodes within the B-TR region can be evaluated by using a linear
 235 mapping from a geometry sequence between 0 and 1:

$$\Xi_j = \frac{1 - q^{j-1}}{1 - q^n} \quad (18)$$

236 to the physical coordinates between \vec{r}_{ht} and \vec{r}_{ref} , where q is the factor to describe the steepness of the
 237 changing element sizes which is usually taken between 1.05 and 1.50. Consider a case where the regions are
 238 respectively divided into 6, 15, 100 layers and the factor $q = 1.20$, an example of the brace mesh is shown
 239 in Fig. 8. It is noticed that the bottom nodes of the brace are exactly overlapped with the upper nodes of
 240 the weld.

Figure 8: Example of a structured mesh of a brace ($n_1 = 3, n_2 = 7, n_3 = 6, q = 1.20$): (a) overview of the brace connected to the weld; (b) a close-up view of the cross section at $z = 0$ with the interface to the weld

241 *2.3. Chord*

242 As mentioned in Hectors and De Waele (2021), among others, the geometry of the chord can be obtained
 243 by wrapping a rectangular plate, and the grid points of the plate can be simply generated through uniform
 244 discretizations with respect to the length (axial), width (circumferential) and thickness directions. For the
 245 modeling of tubular joints, specifically, the nodes at the bottom surface of the weld should also be present on
 246 the chord. This is difficult to perfectly fulfill from such a uniform discretization with hexahedron elements.
 247 Therefore, the chord is partitioned into a number of regions/pieces (recall Fig. 2. Each of the regions/pieces
 248 will next be discretized by a structured mesh using Hexa27n elements.

249 *2.3.1. Chord hot-spot region (C-HS)*

250 Attached to the bottom of the weld, the C-HS zone will be created with a refined element mesh, in order to
 251 allow extraction of the HSS stress near the weld toe. At each polar angle, the nodes at the bottom of the
 252 weld are taken. Based on this, another two reference points P_{in} and P_{out} are created, representing the inner
 253 and outer boundaries of the C-HS zone. The coordinates of P_{in} and P_{out} can be evaluated from Eqs. 13
 254 where the brace radius r is replaced by $r - t - b_{in}$ and $r + b_{out}$, respectively. The parameters b_{in} and b_{out}
 255 characterizing the width of the C-HS zone are automatically determined as $b_{in} = b_{out} = 2t_{chord}$ by default,
 256 which are sufficient to include the local stress points for the hot-spot stress extrapolation in most of the
 257 cases. But still, these are included in the optional parameters where the users are allowed to select their
 258 specified values. A total number of n_{in} uniformly discrete points are then generated between P_{in} and E
 259 (weld), as well as n_{out} points between A (weld) and P_{out} . The inside and outside parts are then discretized
 260 into n_{in} and n_{out} elements along the radial direction. For a given node \vec{r}_t at the outer surface of the chord
 261 (which has been generated from the above), the coordinates of the corresponding node at the inner surface
 262 can be calculated by:

$$\vec{r}_{cb} = \vec{r}_{ct} - \left(\sqrt{y_{ct}^2 + z_{ct}^2} - R + T \right) \vec{n} \quad (19)$$

263 where

$$\vec{n} = \frac{\{0, y_t, z_t\}^T}{\sqrt{y_t^2 + z_t^2}} \quad (20)$$

264 is the unit vector pointing in the outward radial direction of the chord tubular. Based on the weld model
 265 shown in Fig. 6, an example of the attached connection zone is shown in Fig. 9.

Figure 9: Example of a structured mesh of a chord C-HS region ($n_{in} = 2, n_{out} = 3$) attached to the underside of the weld: (a) global geometry of the chord connection zone; (b) cross section at the plane $z = 0$.

266 **2.3.2. Chord plug region (C-PL)**

267 For the plug zone, the grid points are first generated on a flat plane. The exact spatial points in the X - Y - Z
 268 coordinate system are subsequently obtained from the coordinate transformation from the flat plane into a
 269 cylinder. Given that the geometry of the plug zone takes the same topological feature of a circular plate,
 270 the structured mesh cannot be made by directly using hexahedron elements for a uniform grid. In such case,
 271 the plug zone has to be further divided into the central part (C-PL-CT) and the transition part (C-PL-TR).
 272 The C-PL-CT part having the same topological feature as a rectangular plate is created through a uniform
 273 grid. The C-PL-TR part can be further divided into four meshes. As can be seen from Fig. 10, the geometry
 274 of each piece is a curvilinear trapezium, while it should be noticed that one of the edges is curved because
 275 the outer edge takes the shape of the intersection line.

Figure 10: Subdivision of the C-PL-TR part into four transfinite meshes: (a) overview of the mesh strategy; (b) computational domain ξ - η for the transfinite interpolation of the transfinite mesh II as an example.

276 Therefore, each mesh can be generated based on a number of quadrilaterals, where the coordinates of the
 277 grid points are evaluated from the transfinite interpolation:

$$\vec{r} = (1 - \xi)\vec{r}_1 + \xi\vec{r}_t + (1 - \eta)\vec{r}_b + \eta\vec{r}_r - (1 - \xi)(1 - \eta)\vec{r}_1 - \eta(1 - \xi)\vec{r}_2 - \xi\eta\vec{r}_3 - \xi(1 - \eta)\vec{r}_4 \quad (21)$$

278 based on a structured grid on the ξ - η plane, where \vec{r}_1 , \vec{r}_2 , \vec{r}_3 and \vec{r}_4 are the x - y coordinates of the corner
 279 points, and the coordinates of the edge points are calculated by:

$$\vec{r}_t = f(\rho, r, R) \quad (22)$$

$$\vec{r}_b = (1 - \xi)\vec{r}_1 + \xi\vec{r}_4 \quad (23)$$

$$\vec{r}_l = (1 - \eta)\vec{r}_1 + \eta\vec{r}_2 \quad (24)$$

$$\vec{r}_r = (1 - \eta)\vec{r}_4 + \eta\vec{r}_3 \quad (25)$$

280 By uniformly discretizing the plug transition zone into three intervals in the computational domain, an
 281 example of the entire plug zone connecting with the connection zone is shown in Fig. 11.

Figure 11: Example of a structured mesh of a chord connection zone ($n_{in} = 2$, $n_{out} = 3$) attached below the weld: (a) overall geometry of the chord connection zone; (b) cross section at the plane $z = 0$.

282 *2.3.3. Chord transition region (C-TR)*

283 For the chord, a transition region extending outward from the hot-spot region is defined, where its edge
 284 gradually changes from a smooth curve (overlapping with the outer surface of the connection zone) into
 285 four distinct boundary curves. In order to generate a quadrilateral mesh on the reference flat plane, the
 286 transition zone is subdivided into eight transfinite meshes as shown in Fig. 12. For each mesh, the grid
 287 points of a structured mesh can be generated from the transfinite interpolation through Eqs. 21 - 25.

Figure 12: Subdivision of the C-TR region into eight transfinite meshes: (a) overview of the mesh generation; (b) computational domain ξ - η for the transfinite interpolation of the mesh I as an example.

288 As the main focus of the developed model is the stress field near the weld, the element sizes at the locations
 289 far away from the weld are allowed to be larger without loss of accuracy. Being different from the plug
 290 zone (see Fig. 10(b)), the grid points along the η axis, i.e., the radial direction, are therefore generated as a
 291 geometry sequence (from Eq. 18) instead of a uniform grid in the computational domain, while it should be
 292 noted that the number of elements along the circumferential direction $n_\xi = n_\rho/8$ is not independent. After
 293 mapping the grid points from the planar coordinate system ξ - η to the 3D spatial coordinate system X - Y - Z ,
 294 the structured mesh of the transition zone is generated, as shown in Fig. 13.

Figure 13: Example of a structured mesh of a C-TR region ($n_\eta = 3$, $q = 1.15$) attached outside the C-HS region: (a) overall geometry of the mesh; (b) a close-up view to the cross section at the plane $z = 0$.

295 It has to be mentioned that the size of the C-TR region cannot be too large, in order to avoid the distortion
 296 of elements far away from the origin due to the coordinate transformation wrapping the reference flat plate
 297 into a cylinder.

298 *2.3.4. Chord extended region (C-EXT)*

299 Based on the outer edges of the C-TR region as shown in Fig. 13, the regular structured meshes will be
 300 created by extending these edges outward with a certain space interval. First, the edges parallel to the

301 X-axis will be extended along the positive and negative Z-directions, which forms the grid points along
 302 the circumferential direction (i.e., C-EXT-Zp and C-EXT-Zn parts, respectively). Similarly, the edges
 303 perpendicular to the X-axis, resulting from the C-TR, C-EXT-Zn and C-EXT-Zp, are combined and are
 304 extended along the positive and negative X-directions, which form the C-EXT-Xp and C-EXT-Xn parts,
 305 respectively. An example of the C-EXT region is shown in Fig. 14.

Figure 14: Example of the C-EXT region connected to the existing C-TR region of the chord.

306 *2.4. Merge multiple meshes*

307 Once all the meshed regions/parts have been generated (from Secs. 2.1 - 2.3), the entire model of the
 308 elementary joint can be created by merging together all the meshes through node sharing at their interfaces.
 309 Such operation includes the following steps:

- 310 1. Model combination: For the main mesh and an added mesh, the nodal coordinates are collected in the
 311 3-column matrices $nodes_{(main)}$ and $nodes_{(add)}$, respectively. The element connectivities are described
 312 by the 27-column (for Hexa27n) matrices $elements_{(main)}$ and $elements_{(add)}$, respectively. The first step
 313 is to simply stack the node information and the element connectivities such that the added mesh has
 314 been included into the main mesh:

$$nodes = \left\{ \begin{array}{c} nodes_{(main)} \\ nodes_{(add)} \end{array} \right\} \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_n^{(main)} + n_n^{(add)}) \times 3} \quad (26)$$

$$elements = \left\{ \begin{array}{c} elements_{(main)} \\ elements_{(add)} + n_n^{(main)} \end{array} \right\} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{(n_e^{(main)} + n_e^{(add)}) \times 27} \quad (27)$$

315 where $n_n^{(main)}$ and $n_e^{(main)}$ are respectively the total numbers of nodes and elements in the main mesh,
 316 $n_n^{(add)}$ and $n_e^{(add)}$ are respectively the total numbers of nodes and elements in the added mesh.

- 317 2. Node sharing: A list named “*node_update*” is initiated as an integer series from 1 to $n_e^{(main)} + n_e^{(add)}$.
 318 For each node in the added mesh, its distance to each of the nodes in the main mesh will be evaluated.
 319 If a distance smaller than the defined tolerance (which is 10^{-6} by default) is detected, the number of the
 320 overlapping node in the main mesh will be recorded in the second column. Based on the overlapping
 321 node pairs that have been identified, a mapping manipulation will be performed on the list named
 322 “*elements*”, where all overlapping nodes in the added mesh will be replaced by their corresponding
 323 nodes in the main mesh. In such case, the main and added meshes are physically connected.
 324 3. Delete unused nodes: Another list named “*node_unique*” is initiated by collecting all the values in
 325 “*elements*” from smallest to largest, and an integer series is created in the second column. Based on
 326 this, the unused nodes are then deleted by reserving the nodes which have been involved in the first
 327 column of “*node_unique*”, and the element connectivities, i.e., “*elements*”, are then updated from a
 328 mapping manipulation from the values in the first column of “*node_unique*” to its second column.

329 From the above, the Hexa27n mesh of an elementary joint can be generated as long as five mandatory
 330 parameters (r , t , R , T , θ) have been specified. The T-joint is in fact a particular case for $\theta = 90^\circ$.
 331 Such elementary joint will be later used as a fundamental basis for the modeling of more complex joints.
 332 In HFJOINT, a total number of 32 parameters are used to describe the geometry of the elementary joint.
 333 These include 5 mandatory parameters which must be provided by the user, as well as 27 optional parameters
 334 which will be taken by default if not specified. After defining the parameters, the users may generate the
 335 Hexa27n mesh of the elementary joint, as shown in Fig. 15.

Figure 15: Graphical user interface (GUI) for generating elementary joints

336 The node coordinates and element connectivities can be saved as a .pkl file. The detailed explanations of
 337 the parameters are listed in Tab. 1.

Table 1: Geometric parameters (in alphabetical order) defined for the mesh generation of an elementary joint (Note that the mandatory parameters marked with * do not have default values and must therefore be provided from the users.)

Variable description	Default value	Unit
*Brace inclination angle (required)	–	deg
Edge length of the C-PL-CT part (circumferential)	$2r/3$	m
Transit factor of the B-TR region	1.20	–
Transit factor of the C-TR region	1.15	–
Node interval along the axis of the B-HS region	$3t/n_{bhs}$	m
Edge length of the C-PL-CT part (axial)	$2r/3$	m
Edge length of the C-TR region (axial)	$3.5(r+t)$	m
Edge length of the C-TR region (circumferential)	$3.5(r+t)$	m
Length of the B-UN region	$0.25L$	m
Axial length of the B-TR region	$0.25L$	m
Total length of the chord	$2b_{cts}$	m
Number of intervals in the B-UN region	6	–
Number of node intervals in the C-HS region (outward)	6	–
Number of node intervals in the C-HS region (interior)	4	–
Number of nodes along the radius of the C-TR region	5	–
Number of nodes along the radius of the C-PL-TR part	5	–
Number of nodes along the axis of the C-EXT-Xn/Xp part	5	–
Number of nodes along the circumference of the C-EXT-Zn/Zp part	5	–
Number of node intervals along the weld circumference	32	–
Number of nodes through the chord thickness	2	–
Number of intervals along the axis of the B-TR region	10	–
Number of intervals along the radial direction of the weld	2	–
Number of intervals along the upward direction of the weld	2	–
Number of intervals along the axis of the B-HS region	6	–
Inclined angle for the upper edge of the weld cross section	$\pi/6$	rad
The gap between the C-PL region and the weld toe	$2.0T$	m
The gap in height between the chord and the brace	$0.6t$	m
*Outer radius of the brace (required)	–	m
*Outer radius of the chord (required)	–	m
*Wall thickness of the brace (required)	–	m
*Wall thickness of the chord (required)	–	m
The gap between the C-TR region and the weld toe	$2.0T$	m

3. Modeling of complex joints

For complex joints having multiple tubular members, their high-fidelity models can be developed by adding multiple elementary joints into the main mesh. In order to place the elementary joint at the correct position and orientation, three basic transformations are defined in HFJOINT. For the translational motion, all nodes are moved along the same direction with the same distance. The nodal coordinates are calculated as follows:

$$\vec{r}_{mv} = \vec{r}_0 + D\vec{t} \quad (28)$$

where D is the translation distance and \vec{t} is the unit vector of the translation. The 3D rotation can be defined by its Euler angles φ_r , θ and ψ about the global x , y and z axes, respectively. Given the specified values of the rotational angles, the nodal coordinates after the 3D rotation can be evaluated by:

$$\vec{r}_{rt} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \psi_r & -\sin \psi_r & 0 \\ \sin \psi_r & \cos \psi_r & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_r & 0 & \sin \theta_r \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin \theta_r & 0 & \cos \theta_r \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \varphi_r & -\sin \varphi_r \\ 0 & \sin \varphi_r & \cos \varphi_r \end{bmatrix} \vec{r}_0 \quad (29)$$

Alternatively, such 3D rotation can also be defined as a scalar angle ϕ_r about a specified axis described by its direction vector \vec{t} and a known point \vec{r}_p . In such case, the nodal coordinates after the rotation can be

349 evaluated by the Rodrigues' rotation formula:

$$\vec{r}_{rt} = \vec{r}_0 + (\vec{r}_0 - \vec{r}_p) \cos \phi_r + [\vec{t} \times (\vec{r}_0 - \vec{r}_p)] \sin \phi_r + \vec{t} [\vec{t} \cdot (\vec{r}_0 - \vec{r}_p)] (1 - \cos \phi_r) \quad (30)$$

350 For a 3D plane described by its normal unit vector \vec{n} and a reference point \vec{r}_p on the plane, the elementary
 351 joint can be mapped into a symmetric copy across the plane. The nodal coordinates of the transformed
 352 model can be evaluated by:

$$\vec{r}_{mi} = \vec{r}_0 - 2h\vec{n} \quad (31)$$

353 where

$$h = (\vec{r}_0 - \vec{r}_p) \cdot \vec{n} \quad (32)$$

354 is the distance from the original node to the symmetry plane. Based on the elementary joints and the
 355 transformations, a variety of tubular joints with more complex geometric features can be modeled, as shown
 356 in Fig. 16

Figure 16: High-fidelity modeling of typical tubular joints listed in Saini et al. (2016)

357 After the transformation of each elementary joint, the new meshed grid (described by nodal coordinates and
 358 element connectivities) is added into the main mesh through the “merge” function mentioned in Sec. 2.4,
 359 and the final integrated joint model is described by the lists “nodes” and “elements” of the entire model.

360 **4. Finite element formulation**

361 Once the model has been constructed, its stiffness matrix will be evaluated. The external loads including
 362 the nodal forces and imposed displacements can either be converted from an associated beam-element model
 363 or can be defined by the users. The solver allows to return the displacement, stress and strain values for the
 364 entire model.

365 *4.1. Stiffness matrix*

366 From the fundamental finite element theory, the global stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} of the model is obtained from the
 367 linear superposition of each element stiffness matrix \mathbf{K}_e :

$$\mathbf{K} = \sum_{e=1}^{N_e} \mathbf{A}_e^T \mathbf{K}_e \mathbf{A}_e \quad (33)$$

368 where \mathbf{A}_e is the Boolean matrix which maps the local DOFs of the e -th element to the global system. For
 369 each element, the element stiffness matrix is evaluated from the Gaussian quadrature:

$$\mathbf{K}_e = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B} \, d\Omega \approx \sum_{i=1}^{N_G} \sum_{j=1}^{N_G} \sum_{k=1}^{N_G} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B} \Big|_{\xi=g_i, \eta=g_j, \zeta=g_k} w_i w_j w_k \quad (34)$$

370 where \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{D} and \mathbf{J} are the strain matrix, constitutive matrix and Jacobian matrix, respectively. The
 371 locations of the Gauss points and the weight factors are denoted by g and w , respectively. In this work,
 372 the correctness of the global stiffness matrix will be checked ensuring that: (i) the values at the diagonal
 373 positions are all non-zero ($\prod_{i=1}^N K(i, i) \neq 0$) in order to avoid unused free nodes, and, (ii) the matrix is
 374 symmetric ($\max(\text{abs}(\mathbf{K} - \mathbf{K}^T)) < \text{tol}$). Due to inevitable truncation errors, the stiffness matrix may not be
 375 perfectly symmetric. Therefore, the matrix is imposed to be symmetric by eliminating the deviations:

$$\mathbf{K} \leftarrow \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{K}^T + \mathbf{K}) \quad (35)$$

376 *4.2. External loads*

377 In HFJOINT, the external loads involve nodal forces, surface tractions and imposed nodal displacements.
 378 Particularly, the users are allowed to define beam-element forces F_{ax} (axial force), F_{ips} (in-plane shear
 379 force), F_{ops} (out-of-plane shear force), T_b (torsional moment), M_{ipb} (in-plane bending moment) and M_{opb}
 380 (out-of-plane bending moment), as shown in Fig. 17.

Figure 17: Load mapping from beam-element forces to Hexa27n nodal forces: (a) forces applied on the beam cross section; (b) equivalent nodal forces to be evaluated on the loaded surface.

381 The resulting surface tractions acting on the loaded element faces are:

$$\vec{\mathbf{f}}(x, y, z) = \left\{ \sum_{\text{ax,ips,ops}} \frac{F}{A} \vec{\mathbf{t}}_a \right\} + \frac{T_b}{A} \vec{\mathbf{t}}_r + \left\{ \sum_{\text{ipb,opb}} \frac{M}{I} y_c \vec{\mathbf{t}}_b \right\} \quad (36)$$

382 where A is the area of cross section, I is the moment of inertia and y_c is the distance to the neutral surface.
 383 For each loaded element, the equivalent nodal force vector is then evaluated from the Gaussian numerical
 384 integral over the loaded faces. For instance, the equivalent nodal force vector resulting from a traction field
 385 applied on the surface $\zeta = 1$ is evaluated by:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\zeta=1}^{(t)} = \sum_{\xi} \sum_{\eta} \left\{ \mathbf{N}^T \vec{\mathbf{f}} \left| \det(\mathbf{J}_A) \right| w_i w_j \right\} \Big|_{\xi=\xi_i, \eta=\eta_j, \zeta=1} \quad (37)$$

386 Apart from the equivalent nodal forces converted from beam-element forces, the definition of an arbitrary
 387 nodal force vector is also allowed, denoted by $\mathbf{F}^{(n)}$. Considering total nodal forces:

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}^{(t)} + \mathbf{F}^{(n)} \quad (38)$$

388 applied on the model, the equilibrium equation takes the form:

$$\mathbf{K}\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{F} \quad (39)$$

389 which is the standard form of the static finite element formulation.

390 4.3. Boundary conditions

391 Based on this, imposed displacements can be considered for a group of selected DOFs denoted by \mathbf{U}_I , while
 392 the remaining free DOFs to be solved are denoted by \mathbf{U}_F . The equilibrium equation is then rewritten into
 393 the block matrix form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{FF} & \mathbf{K}_{FI} \\ \mathbf{K}_{IF} & \mathbf{K}_{II} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_F \\ \mathbf{U}_I \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{F}_F \\ \mathbf{F}_I \end{Bmatrix} \quad (40)$$

394 It should be mentioned that the additional external forces are not recommended for the imposed DOFs, i.e.,
 395 $\mathbf{F}_I = \mathbf{0}$, because the forces applied on the imposed DOFs are usually dominated by the constraint forces. For
 396 the sake of generality, the entire displacement vector can be described by the least number of independent
 397 DOFs, inspired by the Lagrange's equation of the second kind:

$$\mathbf{U} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{I} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{Bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_F + \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{U}_I \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{P}\mathbf{U}_F + \mathbf{U}_{\text{im}} \quad (41)$$

398 where \mathbf{P} is a Boolean matrix by eliminating the columns corresponding to the imposed DOFs from an N -by- N
 399 identity matrix, and \mathbf{U}_{im} is the global imposed displacement vector (where the values for the free DOFs
 400 are left zero). Note that the fixed boundary condition is in fact a special case of the imposed displacement
 401 where the imposed value is zero.

402 4.4. Static solver

403 By substituting Eq. 41 into Eq. 39, the free DOFs are then solved:

$$\mathbf{U}_F = (\mathbf{P}^T \mathbf{K} \mathbf{P})^{-1} \mathbf{P}^T (\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{K} \mathbf{U}_{\text{im}}) \quad (42)$$

404 The complete displacement vector can then be obtained by substituting the solved \mathbf{U}_F back into Eq. 41.
 405 For each element, the displacements at the element nodes \mathbf{U}_e are extracted from the global displacement
 406 vector \mathbf{U} . The stress at a given location (ξ, η, ζ) can then be evaluated from:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{B}(\xi, \eta, \zeta) \mathbf{U}_e \quad (43)$$

407 In the developed HFJOINT, the element stresses are firstly evaluated at the Gaussian points, resulting in
 408 σ_j (where j is taken from one to the total number of Gaussian points). Based on this, the nodal stresses
 409 can be obtained from an extrapolation. Given the assumption that the distribution of a stress field follows
 410 the superposition of element shape functions, the relationship between the stresses at the nodes $\sigma^{(n)}$ and
 411 Gaussian points $\sigma^{(G)}$ is formulated by:

$$\sigma^{(G)} = \mathbf{T}^{(\sigma)} \sigma^{(n)} \quad (44)$$

412 where

$$T_{i,j}^{(\sigma)} = N_j(\xi_i, \eta_i, \zeta_i) \quad (45)$$

413 is the value of the j -th shape function at the location of the i -th Gaussian point. The inverse matrix of $\mathbf{T}^{(\sigma)}$,
 414 which has been explicitly derived in this work (see Appendix A), allows to extrapolate the stress from the
 415 Gaussian points to the nodes.

416 Based on the solved stress components at the nodes, the signed von Mises stress field is calculated from:

$$\sigma_{vm} = \text{sgn}(\sigma_{xx} + \sigma_{yy} + \sigma_{zz}) \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} [(\sigma_{xx} - \sigma_{yy})^2 + (\sigma_{yy} - \sigma_{zz})^2 + (\sigma_{zz} - \sigma_{xx})^2] + 3(\tau_{xy}^2 + \tau_{yz}^2 + \tau_{xz}^2)} \quad (46)$$

417 for an intuitive visualization, where the signs of the stresses are determined by the traces of their stress
 418 tensors which can be optionally considered during the plot. Within a given mesh grid, the nodal stresses
 419 may not be unique when the node is shared by multiple elements. From the extrapolation of different
 420 adjacent elements, slight deviations are inevitable. In order to avoid this, a dynamic list “*node_stress*”
 421 containing N_{nd} empty elements is initiated. For each element, the nodal stresses are collected into the list,
 422 and the average value of nodal stress is calculated. This will be finally passed into the class “*ModelPlot*”
 423 for the visualization of model deformation and stress field.

424 To determine the HSS stress at the weld toe, the local stresses at the extrapolation points need to be obtained.
 425 In HFJOINT, the stress tensor at a user-specified location (x, y, z) is calculated through interpolation of the
 426 surrounding stress field.

$$\sigma(x, y, z) = N(\xi, \eta, \zeta) \sigma^{(e)} \quad (47)$$

427 where (ξ, η, ζ) are the natural coordinates of the point (x, y, z) in an element having the nodal coordinates:

$$\mathbf{r}^{(e)} = \left\{ \bar{\mathbf{r}}_1^T, \bar{\mathbf{r}}_2^T, \dots, \bar{\mathbf{r}}_N^T \right\}^T \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 3} \quad (48)$$

428 Starting from an initial guess of the natural coordinates, e.g., $\xi = \eta = \zeta = 0.0$, these natural coordinates
 429 can be updated through the iteration below:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \xi_{new} \\ \eta_{new} \\ \zeta_{new} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \xi \\ \eta \\ \zeta \end{Bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \frac{dx}{d\xi} & \frac{dx}{d\eta} & \frac{dx}{d\zeta} \\ \frac{dy}{d\xi} & \frac{dy}{d\eta} & \frac{dy}{d\zeta} \\ \frac{dz}{d\xi} & \frac{dz}{d\eta} & \frac{dz}{d\zeta} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} x_{new} - x \\ y_{new} - y \\ z_{new} - z \end{Bmatrix} \quad (49)$$

430 in order to fulfill that:

$$\bar{\mathbf{r}} = N(\xi, \eta, \zeta) \bar{\mathbf{r}}^{(e)} \quad (50)$$

431 It is known that, for each element, the natural coordinates can always be solved. However, only the element
 432 containing the selected point is needed since the stress should be evaluated from interpolation inside the
 433 element instead of extrapolation from an outside element. Therefore, the iteration (Eq. 49) is performed
 434 taking each element of the model, while the loop is interrupted and the result (ξ, η, ζ) is returned when the
 435 condition:

$$\max(|\xi|, |\eta|, |\zeta|) < 1.0 + \text{tol} \quad (51)$$

436 is satisfied. Note that a tolerance (taken as 0.2 by default) is considered allowing for a slight error of the
 437 given coordinates (x, y, z) (i.e., the specified point is slightly outside the model). By substituting the solved
 438 ξ, η, ζ back into Eq. 47, the stresses at the point (x, y, z) are then obtained.

439 4.5. Postprocessing for HSS stress and stress concentration factors

440 In finite element analysis, the local stress at the weld toe theoretically approaches infinity due to the numerical singularity from the non-smooth feature. For the fatigue assessment of tubular joints, the standardized way of determining the fatigue governing stress at the weld toe is according to the surface stress extrapolation HSS stress approach as described by DNV-RP-C203 DNV (2024). The hot-spot structural stress is computed by extrapolating local stresses extracted at nodes a few distances away from the weld toe (Fig. 18)

Figure 18: Illustration of the linear extrapolation for the evaluation of HSS stress

445 The stress concentration factor (SCF) can then be evaluated as the ratio between the HSS stress and the
446 nominal stress:

$$\text{SCF} = \frac{\sigma_{\text{HS}}}{\sigma_{\text{nm}}} \quad (52)$$

447 where the nominal stresses are the axial stress or maximum bending stress evaluated based on a beam model,
448 given by:

$$\sigma_{\text{nm}} = \begin{cases} \frac{F}{A} & \text{(axial loading case)} \\ \frac{M}{I} \cdot r & \text{(bending cases)} \end{cases} \quad (53)$$

449 The HSS stress of a tubular welded joint is estimated from the linear extrapolation of the stress field within
450 the hot-spot zone:

$$\sigma_{\text{HS}} = \frac{x_2 \bar{\sigma}_1 - x_1 \bar{\sigma}_2}{x_2 - x_1} \quad (54)$$

451 where the distances of the local-stress points (i.e., x_1 and x_2 in Fig. 18) are selected following the DNV-RP-
452 C203 standard DNV (2024), given by:

$$x_1 = 0.2\sqrt{rt} \quad (55)$$

$$x_2 = 0.65\sqrt{rt} \quad (56)$$

453 for the brace side, and

$$x_1 = 0.2\sqrt{rt} \quad (57)$$

$$x_2 = \begin{cases} 0.4\sqrt[4]{rtRT} & \text{(for the crown zone)} \\ \pi R/36 & \text{(for the saddle zone)} \end{cases} \quad (58)$$

454 for the chord side. Since the local stress is a tensor involving six independent components for a 3D case,
455 the scale values are required for $\bar{\sigma}_1$ and $\bar{\sigma}_2$ used in Eq. 54. In most practices, two types of stress fields are

456 considered: the stress normal to the weld toe (which can also be derived from a practical measurement using
 457 strain gauges) and the maximum principal stress (which is often used for assessing fatigue lifetime). The
 458 former one is evaluated from:

$$\bar{\sigma} = n_i \sigma_{ij} n_j = n_x^2 \sigma_{xx} + n_y^2 \sigma_{yy} + n_z^2 \sigma_{zz} + 2n_x n_y \sigma_{xy} + 2n_x n_z \sigma_{xz} + 2n_y n_z \sigma_{yz} \quad (59)$$

459 where $\vec{n} = (n_x, n_y, n_z)$ is the local coordinate system shown in Fig. 4(a) and σ_{ij} is the stress tensor at the
 460 specified location. The maximum principal stress is obtained by taking the absolute maximum eigenvalue
 461 of the stress tensor σ_{ij} .

462 5. Case studies

463 5.1. Case study I - stress concentration factor distribution of a T joint

464 In order to validate the developed HFJOINT numerical tool, a typical T joint (which was also used as a
 465 benchmark in Hectors and De Waele (2021); Yeoh et al. (1995); Soh (1997)) is created for a verification
 466 with respect to the stress concentration factors near the weld. As shown in Fig. 19, the model is created
 467 using the developed Hexa27n elements, and the geometric dimensions and mesh refinement can be seen from
 468 the figure.

Figure 19: Model of the example T joint created in the developed HFJOINT tool

469 For the chord, both the end points are entirely fixed, i.e., the displacements of the nodes at $x = \pm 2065$ mm
 470 are all imposed to be zero, which are considered through the matrix \mathbf{P} plugged in Eq. 42. The joint is loaded
 471 at the free end of the brace. The load cases axial tension ($F = 1$ kN), in-plane bending ($M = 1$ kN · m) and
 472 out-of-plane bending ($M = 1$ kN · m) are firstly defined as beam-element forces, and are then converted into
 473 equivalent nodal forces of the high-fidelity Hexa27n model (see Fig. 20) by projecting the axial (or bending)
 474 stresses onto the shape-function space of each element.

Figure 20: Mapping from beam-element force to nodal forces at the loaded cross section: (a) axial force; (b) in-plane bending moment; (c) out-of-plane bending moment

475 The resulting von Mises stress fields with respect to axial tension, in-plane bending and out-of-plane bending
 476 are shown in Fig. 21.

Figure 21: The signed von Mises stress field of the example T joints subjected to: (a) axial loading; (b) in-plane bending; (c) out-of-plane bending.

477 For the hot-spot zone of the weld at the brace side, the stress state at a specified location can always be
 478 obtained from the interpolation (Eq. 47) as long as the containing element and natural coordinates are found
 479 through Eq. 49.

480 At a set of discrete polar angles ranging from 0° to 90° , such SCFs can always be evaluated by Eq. 52, using
 481 either the normal stress towards the weld toe or the maximum principal stress. Taking the transformed
 482 normal stress, the convergency of the Hexa27n model is first studied through considering different mesh
 483 refinements. The numbers of discretization points n_ρ are taken 32, 48, 64 and 96. The resulting SCFs are
 484 shown in Fig 22, where only half of the region, i.e., $\rho \in [0, 180^\circ]$ is provided because the numerical model is
 485 perfectly symmetric about the $z = 0$ plane.

Figure 22: Convergence of the SCFs with improving mesh refinement: (a) axial tension (brace side); (b) in-plane bending (brace side); (c) out-of-plane bending (brace side); (d) axial tension (chord side); (e) in-plane bending (chord side); (f) out-of-plane bending (chord side).

486 It can be observed that the SCFs approximate the curves for $n_\rho = 96$ with increasing mesh refinement,
 487 confirming the convergence of the Hexa27n model. Compared with the case $n_\rho = 96$, the relative error is
 488 always lower than 5% as long as the weld circumference is discretized into more than 64 intervals. This case
 489 study is executed on a PC (Dell vPRO) with following configurations: CPU 13th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM)
 490 i7-1365U, Memory 16.0 GB 3200 MHz, Python 3.12.2. The stiffness matrices are stored in form of the
 491 compressed sparse row (csr) matrix. By default, they are no longer saved after the nodal displacements have
 492 been solved (Eq. 42). During the analysis, the cost of computational power is summarized in Tab. 2.

Table 2: Summary of the computational cost for the axial loaded case

n_ρ	Number of DOFs		Sparsity of $\mathbf{K}_{g,bc}$	Memory cost for $\mathbf{K}_{g,bc}$ (MB)	CPU time (s)			
	\mathbf{K}_g	$\mathbf{K}_{g,bc}$			\mathbf{K}_g	$\mathbf{K}_{g,bc}$	\mathbf{U}_g	σ_n
32	26388	25740	0.5505 %	41.84	21.13	1.51	5.06	10.94
48	36360	35640	0.3988 %	58.11	50.32	3.92	9.14	27.47
64	46620	45828	0.3108 %	74.86	50.80	3.60	31.50	24.09
96	68004	67068	0.2128 %	109.79	108.32	9.64	71.63	60.58

493 With increasing n_ρ , the memory cost increases, but slightly less than proportional with n_ρ due to the sparse
 494 feature. However, the CPU time significantly increases, especially for the evaluation of the global stiffness
 495 matrix \mathbf{K}_g and the nodal stresses σ_n , because the inverse of the Jacobian matrix needs to be evaluated at each
 496 Gaussian point of each element. For similar cases, the value $n_\rho = 64$ will be recommended considering the
 497 trade off between accuracy (recall Fig. 22) and computational efficiency. By fitting a least-squares line in the
 498 $(\log_{10} n_{DOF}, \log_{10} T_{CPU})$, the complexity of the entire work flow is estimated as $\mathcal{O}(N^{1.89})$, which is slightly
 499 lower than $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ in most standard finite element analysis Szymczak et al. (2013). This is benefited from
 500 the lightweight feature of the HFJOINT solver and the efficient computation with csr matrices. Considering
 501 both the normal stress (after the coordinate transform using Eq. 59) and the maximum principal stress,

502 the resulting SCFs at the brace and chord sides are computed, as shown in Fig. 23. The results are further
 503 compared with a benchmark model developed in Abaqus version v2019 (having an unstructured mesh using
 504 20-node brick elements, C3D20R) Hectors and De Waele (2021), where the SCF distributions are investigated
 505 (see the blue area) based on a group of parameter ranges.

Figure 23: The stress concentration factors along the weld circumference of the example T joint: (a) axial tension (brace side); (b) in-plane bending (brace side); (c) out-of-plane bending (brace side); (d) axial tension (chord side); (e) in-plane bending (chord side); (f) out-of-plane bending (chord side).

506 From the figures, it can be seen that the SCFs evaluated from the normal stress to the weld toe and the
 507 maximum principal stress are close to each other, because the stress is dominated by the bending normal
 508 stress. Exemptions are the SCFs in the weld crown regions for the in-plane bending case (Fig. 23(e)) due to
 509 the significant shear stress component which contributes to the maximum principal stress. It is also worth
 510 mentioning that, for the in-plane bending case, the normal stress is perfectly zero at the saddle (see the
 511 SCFs at 90° and 270° in Fig. 23(b) and 23(e)), and for the out-of-plane bending case, the normal stress
 512 is perfectly zero at the crown (see the SCFs at 0° and 180° in Fig. 23(c) and 23(f)). This is caused by
 513 the neutral surfaces of the bending deformations given that the brace is rather slender. Moreover, the SCF
 514 curves (absolute values) are all symmetric about a 180° shift, since the model is geometrically symmetric
 515 about the plane $x = 0$.

516 For the SCF distributions at the brace side, the results from HFJOINT approximate the lower boundary of
 517 the benchmark model Hectors and De Waele (2021), which corresponds to the welds that had a large cross-
 518 sectional area. In Hectors and De Waele (2021), constrained optimizations were performed at each polar
 519 angle to achieve the minimum and maximum weld cross-section areas within the AWS recommendations.
 520 Such optimization is not included in this work. The weld features are taken $R_w = 0.6T = 7.62$ mm and
 521 $\phi_w = 45^\circ$ for the entire circumference, yielding in the cross-section area overall close to (at places, even
 522 slightly higher than) the maximum case of the AWS recommendations. The SCFs of the HFJOINT model
 523 are therefore slightly lower, especially for the IPB case. For the SCF distributions at the chord side, the
 524 blue values are constrained within narrow ranges due to their lower sensitivities to the weld geometric
 525 parameters. Considering the discrepancy resulting from the optimization, the SCF distributions evaluated
 526 from HFJOINT overall show good agreement with the benchmark model. From the above comparison, the

527 reliability of the developed HFJOINT tool is confirmed.

528 *5.2. Case example II - stress concentration factors of X- and K-joints*

529 In order to further validate the SCFs calculated using HFJOINT, X- and K-joints are selected from Lloyd's
 530 Register of Shipping (1997) where a database of experimental results is provided. From the chord diam-
 531 eter and the remaining non-dimensional parameters characterizing the geometric features of the joints, the
 532 parameters required for HFJOINT modeling inputs are calculated and provided in Tab. 3.

Table 3: Calculation of mandatory modeling parameters for X and K example joints

Joint	Parameters from Ref.						HFJOINT input			
	D	τ	β	γ	α	θ	r_{brace}	t_{chord}	t_{brace}	L_{chord}
X (E30)	508 mm	0.79	0.38	20.7	9.8	90°	96.52 mm	12.27 mm	9.69 mm	2.489 m
K (K-4)	216 mm	0.88	0.47	13.5	10.2	60°	50.76 mm	8.00 mm	7.04 mm	1.266 m

533 Except for the mandatory parameters, the chord length L_{chord} is also specified since it has been provided in
 534 the literature. Additionally, the optional parameter $n_p = 64$ is selected referring to the mesh convergence
 535 studied in Sec. 5.1. For the chord, the nodes on the end cross sections are fully constrained as the boundary
 536 conditions of the model. The load conditions axial tension (AX), in-plane bending moment (IPB) and out-
 537 of-plane bending moment (OPB) are considered. For the X joint, the loads are symmetrically applied on
 538 both the braces, in order to be consistent with the balanced load mentioned in the literature. The von Mises
 539 stress fields are then solved, as shown in Fig 24.

Figure 24: Stress fields of the example joints (where the deformations are largely scaled in order to be visible): (a)(b)(c) X joint; (d)(e)(f) K joint; (a)(d) axial tension; (b)(e) in-plane bending; (c)(f) out-of-plane bending

540 For each load case, the SCFs along the weld circumference, with respect to both the brace and chord
 541 sides, can be obtained by following the HFJOINT workflow, where the normal stresses after the coordinate
 542 transform (Eq. 59) are taken. In Tab. 4, the SCF values at the crown and saddle points are listed, and are
 543 compared with test data provided in literature Lloyd’s Register of Shipping (1997).

Table 4: The SCFs of the X- and K-joints evaluated from HFJOINT (based on the transformed normal stresses, Eq. 59) with comparison to the experimental results Lloyd’s Register of Shipping (1997)

Joint	Approach	AX				IPB				OPB			
		BC	BS	CC	CS	BC	BS	CC	CS	BC	BS	CC	CS
X (E30)	HFJOINT	0.4	7.6	4.5	21.3	1.7	0.0	4.2	0.0	0.0	4.4	0.0	12.2
	Experiment	1.5	10.6	3.3	21.8	2.5	–	4.4	–	–	3.8	–	7.7
K (K-4)	HFJOINT	1.0	2.2	6.5	5.6	1.7	0.0	3.4	0.7	0.0	3.3	0.0	8.6
	Experiment	–	2.3	5.4	3.6	–	–	–	–	–	2.9	–	6.8

544 From Tab. 4, it can be overall concluded that, for most conditions, the SCFs analyzed from HFJOINT
 545 align well with the experimental data. Meanwhile, a few discrepancies can still be noted. For instance, in
 546 out-of-plane bending conditions, the SCFs at the chord (saddle side) are always higher. This may possibly
 547 be caused by the deviations in positioning the strain gauges, used to calculate the experimental SCF values,
 548 which are inevitable in experiments as well as the real geometry of the weld which has sensitive effect to
 549 the distribution of the stress field. Despite this, the overall agreement confirms the reliability of HFJOINT
 550 for analyzing local stress distribution features in welded tubular joints, showing its potential for fatigue
 551 assessment of complex joints having diverse configurations.

552 6. Conclusions

553 In this study, a high-fidelity numerical modeling tool, HFJOINT, is developed for the SCF analysis of
 554 welded tubular joints. Compared with general finite element analysis tools (and softwares), the developed
 555 tool supports for the structured mesh of elementary joints, the creation of complex 3D joints, the mapping
 556 from beam-element forces to Hexa27n nodal forces, the extraction of local stress at an arbitrary point and
 557 the evaluation of weld SCFs at both the chord and brace sides, from a semi-automatic and user-friendly
 558 approach. Especially, the following points are remarked:

- 559 1. The Hexa27n mesh of an elementary joint can be generated automatically as long as the mandatory
 560 parameters (the radius and thickness of chord and brace, as well as the intersection angle) are defined.
 561 The values of the remaining optional parameters will be taken by default rules if not specified.
- 562 2. For the load mapping from beam-element force to the Hexa27n nodal forces, the element nodal force
 563 vectors are evaluated by considering the exact distributions of axial, shear and bending stresses acting
 564 on the loaded cross section.
- 565 3. The SCFs can be evaluated from either the maximum principal stress or the transformed normal
 566 stress perpendicular to the weld toe. The local stress points are automatically selected according to
 567 the DNV DNV (2024) recommendations.
- 568 4. The developed HFJOINT tool is validated through comparison with the SCFs of the benchmark T-,
 569 K- and X- joints obtained from simulation results and test data reported in literature, confirming its
 570 feasibility and potential in fatigue assessment of broader practical welded tubular joints.

571 Based on the developed GUI, a beta version of HFJOINT will soon be available online. The documentation
 572 has been made available on the Github website Zhang et al. (2025) and will be periodically updated in the
 573 future.

574 **Acknowledgments**

575 This work is part of the FLOATFARM project, funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research
576 and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101136091.

577 **Appendix A. The constant matrix for stress extrapolation**

578 The natural coordinates of the nodes in each Hexa27n element are ordered as shown in Tab. A.5.

Table A.5: Natural coordinates of the nodes in a Hexa27n element

Nodes 1–9					Nodes 10–18					Nodes 19–27				
No.	ξ	η	ζ	type	No.	ξ	η	ζ	type	No.	ξ	η	ζ	type
1	-1	-1	-1	corner	10	1	0	-1	edge center	19	1	1	0	edge center
2	1	-1	-1	corner	11	0	1	-1	edge center	20	-1	1	0	edge center
3	1	1	-1	corner	12	-1	0	-1	edge center	21	-1	0	0	face center
4	-1	1	-1	corner	13	0	-1	1	edge center	22	1	0	0	face center
5	-1	-1	1	corner	14	1	0	1	edge center	23	0	-1	0	face center
6	1	-1	1	corner	15	0	1	1	edge center	24	0	1	0	face center
7	1	1	1	corner	16	-1	0	1	edge center	25	0	0	-1	face center
8	-1	1	1	corner	17	-1	-1	0	edge center	26	0	0	1	face center
9	0	-1	-1	edge center	18	1	-1	0	edge center	27	0	0	0	element center

579 Given the stresses at the Gaussian points $\sigma^{(G)}$, the nodal stresses $\sigma^{(n)}$ can then be evaluated from the
580 extrapolation:

$$\sigma^{(n)} = [\mathbf{T}^{(\sigma)}]^{-1} \sigma^{(G)} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

581 By substituting the shape functions (associated with the natural coordinates listed in Tab. A.5) into the
582 stress interpolation formulated in Eq. 44, the stress extrapolation matrix $[\mathbf{T}^{(\sigma)}]^{-1}$ has been explicitly solved
583 as:

$$[\mathbf{T}^{(\sigma)}]^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 3.234 & -1.458 & 0.411 & -1.458 & 0.657 & -0.185 & 0.411 & -0.185 & 0.052 & -1.458 & 0.657 & -0.185 & 0.657 & -0.296 & 0.083 & -0.185 & 0.083 & -0.024 & 0.411 & -0.185 & 0.052 & -0.185 & 0.083 & -0.024 & 0.052 & -0.024 & 0.052 \\ 0.411 & -0.185 & 0.052 & -0.185 & 0.083 & -0.024 & 0.411 & -0.185 & 0.052 & -0.185 & 0.657 & -0.185 & 0.657 & -0.296 & 0.083 & -0.185 & 0.083 & -0.024 & 3.234 & -1.458 & 0.411 & -1.458 & 0.657 & -0.185 & 0.411 & -0.185 & 0.052 \\ 0.052 & -0.024 & 0.007 & -0.185 & 0.083 & -0.024 & 0.411 & -0.185 & 0.052 & -0.185 & 0.083 & -0.024 & 0.657 & -0.296 & 0.083 & -1.458 & 0.657 & -0.185 & 0.411 & -0.185 & 0.052 & -1.458 & 0.657 & -0.185 & 3.234 & -1.458 & 0.411 \\ 0.411 & -0.185 & 0.052 & -1.458 & 0.657 & -0.185 & 3.234 & -1.458 & 0.411 & -0.185 & 0.083 & -0.024 & 0.657 & -0.296 & 0.083 & -1.458 & 0.657 & -0.185 & 0.052 & -0.024 & 0.007 & -0.185 & 0.083 & -0.024 & 0.411 & -0.185 & 0.052 \\ 0.411 & -1.458 & 3.234 & -1.458 & 0.657 & -1.458 & 0.052 & -0.185 & 0.411 & -0.185 & 0.657 & -1.458 & 0.083 & -0.296 & 0.657 & -0.024 & 0.083 & -0.185 & 0.052 & -0.185 & 0.411 & -0.024 & 0.083 & -0.185 & 0.007 & -0.024 & 0.052 \\ 0.052 & -0.185 & 0.411 & -0.024 & 0.083 & -0.185 & 0.007 & -0.024 & 0.052 & -0.185 & 0.657 & -1.458 & 0.083 & -0.296 & 0.657 & -0.024 & 0.083 & -0.185 & 0.411 & -1.458 & 3.234 & -1.458 & 0.657 & -0.185 & 0.411 & -0.185 & 0.411 \\ 0.007 & -0.024 & 0.052 & -0.024 & 0.083 & -0.185 & 0.052 & -0.185 & 0.411 & -0.024 & 0.083 & -0.185 & 0.083 & -0.296 & 0.657 & -0.185 & 0.657 & -1.458 & 0.052 & -0.185 & 0.411 & -0.185 & 0.657 & -1.458 & 0.411 & -1.458 & 3.234 \\ 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 2.187 & -0.986 & 0.278 & -0.986 & 0.444 & -0.125 & 0.278 & -0.125 & 0.035 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 \\ 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.278 & -0.125 & 0.035 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & -0.986 & 0.444 & -0.125 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0.000 & -0.986 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.278 & 0.000 & 0.000 & -0.986 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 2.187 & 0.000 & 0.000 \\ 0.000 & 0.278 & 0.000 & 0.000 & -0.986 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 2.187 & 0.000 & 0.000 & -0.125 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.444 & 0.000 & 0.000 & -0.986 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.035 & 0.000 & 0.000 & -0.125 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.278 & 0.000 & 0.000 \\ 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 1.479 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & -0.667 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.188 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 \\ 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.188 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & -0.667 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 1.479 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 \\ 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 1.479 & 0.000 & 0.000 & -0.667 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.188 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 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0.000 & 0.000 & 1.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 & 0.000 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

584 for evaluating the Hexa27n nodal stresses from the stresses at the Gaussian points.

585 **References**

586 AWS, 2025. D1.1/D1.1M:2025 - Structural Welding Code - Steel. American Welding Society.
587 Becker, J.M., Gerberich, W.W., Bouwkamp, J.G., 1972. Fatigue failure of welded tubular joints. Journal of the Structural
588 Division 98, 37–59.
589 Chen, T.Y., Zhang, H.Y., 1996. Stress analysis of spatial frames with consideration of local flexibility of multiplanar tubular
590 joint. Engineering Structures 18, 465–471.

- 591 DNV, 2024. DNV-RP-C203: Fatigue design of offshore steel structures - Recommended practice (Edition 2024-10). Det Norske
592 Veritas (DNV): Oslo, Norway.
- 593 Hasan, M.T., Mia, M.J., Bipul, M.S.I., 2024. Finite element analysis of tubular KK joint under compressive loading. *American*
594 *Journal of Computational Mathematics* 14, 291–304.
- 595 Hectors, K., De Waele, W., 2020. A numerical framework for determination of stress concentration factor distributions in
596 tubular joints. *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences* 174, 105511.
- 597 Hectors, K., De Waele, W., 2021. Influence of weld geometry on stress concentration factor distributions in tubular joints.
598 *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* 176, 106376.
- 599 Lee, C., Chiew, S., Lie, S., Nguyen, T., 2010. Adaptive mesh generation procedures for thin-walled tubular structures. *Finite*
600 *Elements in Analysis and Design* 46, 114–131.
- 601 Lee, M., 1999. Strength, stress and fracture analyses of offshore tubular joints using finite elements. *Journal of Constructional*
602 *Steel Research* 51, 265–286.
- 603 Li, G., Li, Z.N., Zeng, Q., Guo, X.N., 2024. Shape optimization of cast steel tubular joints based on subdivision surface and
604 genetic algorithm. *Thin-Walled Structures* 204, 112258.
- 605 Li, Y., Zhou, X.P., Qi, Z.M., Zhang, Y.B., 2014. Numerical study on girth weld of marine steel tubular piles. *Applied Ocean*
606 *Research* 44, 112–118.
- 607 Lie, S.T., Lee, C.K., Wong, S., 2003. Model and mesh generation of cracked tubular Y-joints. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*
608 70, 161–184.
- 609 Lloyd's Register of Shipping, 1997. *Stress Concentration Factors for Simple Tubular Joints: Assessment of Existing and*
610 *Development of New Parametric Formulae*. Offshore Technology Report OTH 354. Health and Safety Executive. London.
611 Prepared by Lloyd's Register of Shipping for the Health and Safety Executive.
- 612 Marshall, P., Qian, X.D., Nguyen, C., Petchdemanengam, Y., 2013. Welder-optimized CJP-equivalency welds for tubular
613 connections. *Welding in the World* 57, 569–579.
- 614 Marshall, P.W., 2013. *Design of welded tubular connections: Basis and use of AWS code provisions*. volume 37. Elsevier.
- 615 N'diaye, A., Hariri, S., Pluvinage, G., Azari, Z., 2009. Stress concentration factor analysis for welded, notched tubular T-joints
616 under combined axial, bending and dynamic loading. *International Journal of Fatigue* 31, 367–374.
- 617 Oberrecht, S., Novák, J., Krysl, P., 2014. B-bar FEMs for anisotropic elasticity. *International Journal for Numerical Methods*
618 *in Engineering* 98, 92–104.
- 619 Qian, X., Romeijn, A., Wardenier, J., Choo, Y., 2002. An automatic FE mesh generator for CHS tubular joints, in: *ISOPE*
620 *International Ocean and Polar Engineering Conference, ISOPE*. pp. ISOPE-I.
- 621 Saini, D.S., Karmakar, D., Ray-Chaudhuri, S., 2016. A review of stress concentration factors in tubular and non-tubular joints
622 for design of offshore installations. *Journal of Ocean Engineering and Science* 1, 186–202.
- 623 Sandal, K., Verbart, A., Stolpe, M., 2018. Conceptual jacket design by structural optimization. *Wind Energy* 21, 1423–1434.
- 624 Soh, A., 1997. An improved procedure for the determination of hot spot stresses in tubular joints. *Fatigue & Fracture of*
625 *Engineering Materials & Structures* 20, 1709–1718.
- 626 Szymczak, A., Paszyńska, A., Gurgul, P., Paszyński, M., 2013. Graph grammar based direct solver for hp-adaptive finite
627 element method with point singularities. *Procedia Computer Science* 18, 1594–1603.
- 628 Udomworarat, P., Miki, C., Ichikawa, A., Komechi, M., Mitsuki, K., Hosaka, T., 2002. Fatigue performance of composite
629 tubular K-joints for truss type bridge. *Structural Engineering/Earthquake Engineering* 19, 65–79.
- 630 Vigh, L.G., Dunai, L., 2004. Finite element modelling and analysis of bolted joints of 3D tubular structures. *Computers &*
631 *Structures* 82, 2173–2187.
- 632 Vignesh Chellappan, N., Nallayarasu, S., 2019. Residual strength of cracked tubular joint using nonlinear finite element analysis,
633 in: *Proceedings of the Fourth International Conference in Ocean Engineering (ICOE2018) Volume 2*, Springer. pp. 395–416.
- 634 Woghiren, C., Brennan, F.P., 2009. Weld toe stress concentrations in multi-planar stiffened tubular KK joints. *International*
635 *Journal of Fatigue* 31, 164–172.
- 636 Yeoh, S.K., Soh, A.K., Soh, C.K., 1995. Behaviour of tubular T-joints subjected to combined loadings. *Journal of Constructional*
637 *Steel Research* 32, 259–280.
- 638 Zavvar, E., Hectors, K., De Waele, W., 2021. Stress concentration factors of multi-planar tubular kt-joints subjected to in-plane
639 bending moments. *Marine Structures* 78, 103000.
- 640 Zhang, S.H., Hectors, K., De Waele, W., 2025. HFJOINT - Documentation and user guidelines. URL: [https://github.ugent.
641 be/pages/SOZHANG/mytool-docs/](https://github.ugent.be/pages/SOZHANG/mytool-docs/).
- 642 Zheng, Y.K., Chen, Z.H., Qian, H.L., Wang, P., Cao, Z.G., 2024. A shell equilibrium modeling for stress distribution of offshore
643 tubular joints. *International Journal of Pressure Vessels and Piping* 212, 105334.

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